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Review article

Effect size and land-requirements of plant-based feeding interventions to reduce methane emissions from cattle and sheep in European subalpine regions

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ABSTRACT

In the past decades, hundreds of scientific studies have aimed at identifying feeding interventions to reduce the production of enteric methane (CH₄) from ruminant livestock. However, mitigation measures for extensive grassland-based ruminant production systems are largely lacking, or are hardly transferred into practice. The aim of this study was to determine the effect size of plant-based feeding interventions in cattle and sheep, and to assess the feasibility of implementation by calculating the agricultural area required to grow these products. A literature research was carried out to identify plant-based feeding interventions, where the effect size was determined by at least three publications measuring CH₄ *in vivo* in cattle or sheep, and which could be grown in temperate Europe. Using Switzerland as an example for a country with low availability of arable land and representative for grass-based ruminant production systems, it was estimated how much agricultural land would be required to grow these plant products in sufficient quantities to achieve the effects in the entire population of Swiss cattle or sheep. The review revealed that the evident effect size of plant-based feeding interventions in cattle reached only in few cases an average reduction in CH₄ per unit dry matter intake (DMI) of 20%, and often stayed below 10%. For sheep, one intervention (*Lotus ssp.*) exceeded 30% reduction of methanogenesis, the others fitted into the results for cattle. The calculations revealed that for many products, the area required to supply them to the entire Swiss cattle population would exceed the current national area of arable land. For the effective plant-based products identified for sheep, much less agricultural land would be required, due to the small population size. Given the low efficacy of the interventions and the vast requirements for land resources to produce the respective plants, the cost of implementing them appears to exceed the benefit in greenhouse gas reduction. While feeding products of arable cultures appear hardly feasible for CH₄ mitigation, implementing effective pasture plants in existing grasslands may be more practicable. Despite their comparably low efficacy to reduce CH₄, including plants rich in plant secondary metabolites into multispecies swards would be a feasible approach with comparatively low risks and further benefits. Overall, the calculations reveal that the implementation of plant-based CH₄ mitigators may largely increase the competition for the use of agricultural land, which is the opposite of intentions with grassland-based dairy and meat production, and which affects climate change as well.

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1. Introduction

Due to its properties as a greenhouse gas, methane (CH₄) enterically produced by ruminant livestock has received increasing interest from the scientific community (Arndt et al., 2022; Beauchemin et al., 2008; Knapp et al., 2014), policy makers and agricultural professionals. With the current goals to reduce global warming, much effort has gone into investigating measures to reduce enteric CH₄ emission from ruminants. In the past 40 years, the number of publications on this topic has increased almost exponentially (Fig. 1), and the investigated options to reduce enteric CH₄ production include feeding strategies, breeding for low emitting animals, increasing animal longevity, or dietary supplementation of compounds inhibiting ruminal methanogenesis. Several comprehensive review articles have recently been published with the aim to collate viable mitigation methods and to assess their efficacy. One of the most recent articles (Arndt et al., 2022) identified several measures which have shown promising results in *in vivo* trials. Among them are strategies such as reducing the amount of fibre in the ruminant's diet (which is the main substrate for CH₄-formation) by decreasing the ratio of roughage to concentrates, or the supplementation with synthetic CH₄ inhibitors (e.g. 3-NOP), Ionophores (Monensin) or Nitrate. While the efficacy of these methods is promising, they are not suitable for all ruminant production systems. In particular, extensive grass-based systems with a high emphasis on low input of external nutrients, animal welfare and sustainability (e.g. organic farming) require different assessments and solutions (Eugène et al., 2021; Zeitz et al., 2012). Mitigation through reducing dietary roughage:concentrate proportions is contrary to targets of grassland-based production (Leiber, 2022). Feed additives or a change of the basal ration can be practicable for intensive husbandry systems, where the composition of the diet can be monitored and controlled, and where it is offered at a constant rate to each animal. However, implementing additives in pasture-based systems is a challenge, as the animals show a higher variability in intake and diet composition and a constant administration of feed additives is much more challenging. Furthermore, synthetic feed additives are not allowed in organic agriculture (Varga et al., 2022), and for reasons of feed-food competition the use of higher concentrate amounts is criticized for having only limited positive effects on larger scale system models (Schader et al., 2015). Herb-based approaches, which often rely on the modulating effects of plant secondary compounds in the rumen appear as interesting options, and are frequently assessed and reported (Beauchemin et al., 2008; Khiaosa-Ard and Zebeli, 2013; Min et al., 2020). However, some of these approaches may not be viable due to low availability, production costs, unsustainable production, or because they are also in competition with human food production due to limited arable land resources. Moreover, realistic figures of production conditions for such plants containing effective CH₄ mitigating substances have rarely been assessed or estimated. Most of the experimental studies available do not ask the question of feasibility of production, nor do large comprehensive reviews (Arndt et al., 2022; Min et al., 2020). Thus, proposed measures for mitigation of CH₄ on the basis of plant feed additives most often lack evidence of practical feasibility.

The aim of this review was therefore to collate mitigation options through plant-based feeding interventions and to assess their effectiveness and the feasibility of implementation, focusing on the area required to grow the product in question. The latter was assessed based on the example of Switzerland, where grassland-based animal production is predominant and crucial (Hofstetter et al., 2014; Leiber et al., 2017) due to the limited availability of arable land. At the same time, the limitations in arable land in Switzerland set limits for producing feed additives within the region. Therefore, Switzerland appears to be a model specific for subalpine and mountainous regions in Europe, but the basic challenge may be elucidated for other regions short in arable land and with a high prevalence of ruminant livestock. By reporting the potential effects together with the agricultural areas required to realize them, this approach aims at contributing to the discussion about the urgently needed implementation of decades-long research efforts on the topic.

Fig. 1. Number of scientific publications on CH₄ production in ruminants from 1980 to 2022. The data are based on a Web of Science search including the search terms 'methane' and 'ruminant'.

Table 1

List of the plant species or process-based interventions, which were assessed in the publications selected for this literature review.

Plant species	Material used for feeding experiments	N studies investigating product		References
		Cattle	Sheep	
<i>Allium sativum</i>	Leaves, bulb, extract	3	3	Kim et al. (2018);Ma et al. (2016);Meale et al. (2014);Panthee et al. (2017);Staerfl et al. (2012);van Zijderveld et al. (2011)
<i>Astragalus cicer</i>	Whole plant	1	0	Stewart et al. (2019)
<i>Brassica campestris</i>	Fodder	0	2	Sun et al. (2014);Sun et al. (2012)
<i>Brassica napus</i>	Seed, oil, expeller, fodder	8	4	Bayat et al. (2018);Beauchemin and McGinn (2006);Brask et al. (2013);Gidlund et al., (2015, 2017);Hellwing et al. (2012);Machmüller et al. (2000);Moate et al. (2011);Pinares-Patiño et al. (2016);Sun et al. (2015);Sun et al. (2014);Sun et al. (2012)
<i>Brassica oleracea</i>	Fodder	0	1	Sun et al. (2012)
<i>Calluna vulgaris</i>	Whole plant	0	1	Pérez-Barbería et al. (2020)
<i>Carthamus tinctorius</i>	Oil	1	0	Bayat et al. (2018)
<i>Carum carvi</i>	Oil	1	0	Lejonklev et al. (2016)
<i>Castanea sativa</i>	Extract	1	0	Aboagye et al. (2019)
<i>Cichorium intybus</i>	Whole plant	0	4	Niderkorn et al. (2019);Sun et al. (2011);Sun et al. (2012);Waghorn et al. (2002)
<i>Corylus avellana</i>	Leaves	1	1	Terranova et al. (2021); S.Wang et al. (2018)
<i>Eutrema japonicum</i>	Oil	1	0	Mohammed et al. (2004)
<i>Glycine max</i>	Beans, meal, oil	5	3	Beck et al. (2019);Boland et al. (2020);Fiorentini et al. (2014);Gidlund et al. (2015);Lima et al. (2019); V.Lind et al. (2020);Mao et al. (2010);Neto et al. (2015)
<i>Hedysarum coronarium</i>	Whole plant	1	1	Waghorn et al. (2002);Woodward et al. (2002)
<i>Helianthus annuus</i>	Oil, seeds	6	1	Bayat et al. (2017);Beauchemin et al. (2007);Chuntrakort et al. (2014);Machmüller et al. (2000);Mata e Silva et al. (2017);McGinn et al. (2004);Woodward et al. (2006)
<i>Hordeum vulgare</i>	Seeds	0	1	Moss and Givens (2002)
<i>Juniperus sp.</i>	Oil	1	0	Meale et al. (2014)
<i>Linum usitatissimum</i>	Seeds, oil, extrudate	14	1	Bayat et al. (2018);Benchaar et al. (2015);Boland et al. (2020);Fiorentini et al. (2014);Focant et al. (2019);Hammond et al. (2015);Hassanat and Benchaar (2021);Machmüller et al. (2000);Martin et al., (2008, 2016);Pinares-Patiño, Ulyatt et al. (2003);Poteko et al. (2020);van Gastelen et al. (2017);van Zijderveld et al. (2011);Veneman et al. (2015)
<i>Lotus sp.</i>	Whole plant	6	3	Dini et al. (2012);Hammond et al. (2014);Lagrange et al. (2020);Pinares-Patiño, Ulyatt et al. (2003);Stewart et al. (2019);Waghorn et al. (2002);Woodward et al., (2001, 2004)
<i>Lupinus sp.</i>	Beans	1	0	Staerfl et al. (2012)
<i>Medicago sativa</i>	Whole plant	6	2	Chaves et al. (2006);Doreau et al. (2014);Gere et al. (2021);Hassanat et al. (2014);McCaughy et al. (1999);Stewart et al. (2019);Waghorn et al. (2002);Woodward et al. (2001)
<i>Morus sp.</i>	Extract	0	2	Chen et al. (2015);Ma et al. (2017)
<i>Onobrychis sp.</i>	Whole plant	5	1	Bouchard et al. (2015);Chung et al. (2013);Huyen et al. (2016);Lagrange et al. (2020);Niderkorn et al. (2019);Stewart et al. (2019)
<i>Origanum vulgare</i>	Leaves, extract	7	2	Benchaar (2020);Hristov et al. (2013);Kolling et al. (2018);Lejonklev et al. (2016);Olijhoek et al. (2019);Stefenoni et al. (2021);Tekippe et al. (2011); C. J.Wang et al. (2009);Zhang et al. (2021)
<i>Raphanus sativus</i>	Whole plant	0	1	Sun et al. (2014)
<i>Sanguisorba minor</i>	Whole plant	1	0	Stewart et al. (2019)
<i>Sorghum sp.</i>	Whole plant	2	0	de Oliveira et al. (2007);Gere et al. (2021)
<i>Tagetes erecta</i>	Whole plant	1	0	Pineda et al. (2018)
<i>Trifolium pratense</i>	Whole plant	4	3	Gidlund et al. (2017);Hammond et al. (2014);Kasuya and Takahashi (2010);Niderkorn et al. (2015);Niderkorn et al. (2019);van Dorland et al. (2007);Waghorn et al. (2002)
<i>Trifolium repens</i>	Whole plant	4	4	Enriquez-Hidalgo et al. (2014);Hammond et al. (2013);Hammond et al. (2014);Lee et al. (2004); V.Lind et al. (2020);Niderkorn et al. (2017);Ulyatt et al. (1988);van Dorland et al. (2007)
<i>Triticum sp.</i>	Whole plant silage	1	0	McGeough et al. (2010)
<i>Vaccinium myrtillus</i>	Whole plant	0	1	Pérez-Barbería et al. (2020)
<i>Vicia faba</i>	Beans	1	0	Cherif et al. (2018)
<i>Vitis vinifera</i>	Grape marc	3	0	Caetano et al. (2019);Moate et al., (2014, 2020)

(continued on next page)

Table 1 (continued)

Plant species	Material used for feeding experiments	N studies investigating product		References
		Cattle	Sheep	
<i>Zea mays</i>	Whole plant, silage, seeds, oil	21	0	Benchaar et al., (2014, 2015);Brask et al. (2013);Dall-Orsoletta et al. (2019);Doreau et al. (2014);Hammond et al. (2015);Hart et al. (2014);Hassanat et al., (2013, 2017);Hatew et al. (2015);Hindrichsen et al. (2006);Judy et al. (2019);Lettat et al. (2013);Moate et al. (2011);Na et al. (2013);Schwarm et al. (2015);Staerfl et al. (2012);Uddin et al. (2020);van Dorland et al. (2007);van Gastelen et al. (2015)
Other plant-based products		N studies investigating product		References
		Cattle	Sheep	
Biochar		2	1	L.Lind et al. (2020);Terry et al. (2019);Winders et al. (2019)
Brewers grains		2	0	Duthie et al. (2015);Moate et al. (2011)
Carvacol		1	0	Benchaar (2020)
DDGS		6	0	Benchaar et al. (2013);Bernier et al. (2012);Garnsworthy et al. (2021);Hoffmann et al. (2021);Judy et al. (2019);McGinn et al. (2009)
Essential oil blends		5	0	Alemu et al. (2019);Beauchemin and McGinn (2006);Castro-Montoya et al. (2015);Hart et al. (2019);Tomkins et al. (2015)
High quality pasture or forage		2	5	Archimède et al. (2018);Boadi and Wittenberg (2002);Fraser et al. (2014);Jonker et al., (2014, 2018);Ulyatt et al. (2005);Zhao et al. (2017)
Industry byproducts		1	0	Pang et al. (2018)
Mixed concentrates supplementation or increase in ration		12	3	Aguerre et al. (2011);Barbero et al. (2015);Chong et al. (2014);Ferris et al. (2020);Hoffmann et al. (2021);Jiao et al. (2014);Liu et al. (2013);Lovett et al. (2005);Muñoz et al. (2015);Neto et al. (2015);Patel et al. (2011);Pedreira et al. (2013);Silvestre et al. (2021);van Wyngaard et al. (2018); C.Wang et al. (2007)
Mixed legume forages	Hay, pasture	2	0	Boadi and Wittenberg (2002);Dini et al. (2018)
Multispecies pasture containing clover, plantain, chicory and other species		4	0	Carmona-Flores et al. (2020);Jonker et al. (2019);Loza et al. (2021);Wilson et al. (2020)
Partial mixed ration		1	0	O'Neill et al. (2012)
Resveratrol		0	1	Chen et al. (2015)
Tannin pellets		1	0	Focant et al. (2019)
Processes		N studies investigating product		References
		Cattle	Sheep	
Decrease maturity of cut forage		7	1	Brask et al. (2013);Chung et al. (2013);Hironaka et al. (1996);Kasuya and Takahashi (2010);Machado et al. (2015);Pang et al. (2018);Warner et al. (2017)
Decrease pasture maturity		10	2	Barbero et al. (2015);Boland et al. (2013);Congio et al. (2018);Hart et al. (2009);Kidane et al. (2018);Molano and Clark (2008);Muñoz et al. (2016);Pinares-Patiño, Baumont et al. (2003);Ramírez-Restrepo et al. (2020);Warner et al., (2016, 2015);Wims et al. (2010)
Grazing vs conserved forage silage or TMR		2	5	Chong et al. (2014);Dall-Orsoletta et al. (2016);Liu et al. (2013);McDonnell et al. (2016);Pinares-Patiño, Ulyatt et al. (2003);Santoso et al. (2007);Zhao et al. (2016)
Increase feeding frequency		1	0	Jonker et al. (2016)
Increase grazing pressure		4	1	Chiavegato et al. (2015);de Souza Filho et al. (2019);DeRamus et al. (2003);McCaughey et al. (1997);Savian et al. (2014)
Increase intake		6	4	Boadi and Wittenberg (2002);Goopy et al. (2020);Hammond et al. (2014);Hironaka et al. (1996);Jonker et al., (2014, 2016);O'Neill et al. (2012);Sun et al. (2012);Warner et al. (2017);Yang et al. (2021)
Increase maize maturity		3	0	Hatew et al. (2016);McGeough et al. (2010);Nishida et al. (2007)
Milling or pelleting forage		1	2	Hironaka et al. (1996);Zhao et al., (2016, 2017)
Nitrogen fertilization of pasture		2	1	Amaral et al. (2016);Warner et al., (2015, 2016)
Rotational stocking		1	2	McCaughey et al. (1997);Savian et al., (2014, 2018)
Spatial separation of forages		1	0	Carmona-Flores et al. (2020)

2. Material & methods

2.1. Search strategy, selection of publications, calculation of effect size

In an in-depth literature research, data was collated on CH₄ reduction potential of plant-based feeding interventions and supplements. The initial search was carried out on Web of science, Pubmed and Google Scholar, using the terms “enteric”, “methane”, “ruminant” in different combinations. Once a certain feeding intervention was identified, a specific search for further publications was carried out by using the search terms “[feeding intervention]”, “methane”, “ruminant”. Furthermore, the references given in relevant recent reviews and studies on specific interventions were screened for additional publications. Publications to be included in the database were selected based on the following criteria: in vivo CH₄ measurements with established methods (respiration chamber, SF6, head hoods or boxes, e.g. Greenfeed®); relevant ruminant grazer-type livestock species, i.e. cattle or sheep; information on diet composition and DMI available; investigation of an intervention and a control treatment to allow the calculation of the percentage in decrease or increase of CH₄ emissions; sound study design (e.g. randomized block, Latin square, cross-over); peer-reviewed publication. Due to the different study designs of the included publications, some investigated the effect of the potential mitigator in the same animals on different diets, while others assessed their effect in different groups of animals, where one would receive a control diet and the other the treatment diet. For each of the publications, the control treatment was considered the diet defined as control by the respective authors. For stabled animals, this was generally the basal diet without the plant-based additive. In studies where the effect of a certain type of concentrates was assessed, the control diet consisted of either the diet without concentrates or the diet with a different type of concentrates. In studies where the effect of a certain pasture composition was studied, the control was generally a pasture without the studied plants, e.g. pure ryegrass or grass-clover compared to multispecies swards. It has to be noted, that the control and basal diet often differed between studies assessing the same plant-based feeding intervention, which probably added to the variability in the results. It has previously been shown that absolute enteric CH₄ production is highly correlated with DMI (Hammond et al., 2013; Niu et al., 2018; van Lingen et al., 2019), therefore, publications which provided absolute emissions per animal without information on DMI were excluded. While DMI reported for experiments performed indoors or with animals fed individually is generally accurate, the assessment of DMI on pasture is more challenging and less precise (e.g. by using fecal markers or by measuring pre- and post-grazing herbage mass). Although all publications included in this review were peer-reviewed, it should be noted that the lack of methods to accurately quantify intake in grazing animals may have added some variability to the data.

Only plant-based interventions were included (exclusion of animal products, synthetic substances, ionophores, micro-organisms, or antibiotics). Measures were only included, if they could be implemented in temperate climatic regions, e.g. if there was evidence for successful cultivation of the crop or plant species in temperate climatic regions; products based on tropical plants (e.g. coconut, acacia, tea, tropical algae) were excluded. Furthermore, studies where animals received a diet with more than 40% concentrates were excluded, as this is the upper limit for concentrates in the EU Organic Regulations (European Commission, 2018) and this amount of concentrates is seldom exceeded in grass-based systems (Muñoz et al., 2018). Approximately 2000 publications were screened initially based on their title and abstract, 369 of which were downloaded for further screening and 183 of which met the inclusion criteria and were included in the database. The following information was gathered from all publications: type of intervention, composition of the control diet, animal species, number of animals per treatment, experimental design, inclusion rate of the tested feed components

Fig. 2. Number of publications included in the analysis in this review divided by the country in which the experiments had been conducted.

Table 2

^aEvaluation of the amount and area required to supply the entire Swiss sheep and cattle population with selected plant-based feed products previously assessed for their potential to reduce CH₄ emissions.

Product	Number of studies included	Mean reduction CH ₄ per g/kg DMI	±SD	Mean inclusion rate in ration reported in these studies	Daily required amount per head	Annual amount required for entire Swiss population	Estimated annual yield of product in CH	Area required to grow product for entire Swiss population	Swiss arable or grassland* area required to grow product for entire population	References for yield estimate
		%	%	DM %	DM kg/day	DM t/year	DM t/ha	ha	%	
Cattle										
Brassica napus (expeller)	3	1.7	8.1	13.7	2.1	1134613	1.8	620007	157	Agristat (2022)
Brassica napus (oil)	3	14.8	3.0	5.7	0.9	472832	1.2	404130	102	Agristat (2022)
Helianthus annuus (oil)	5	19.6	5.4	4.0	0.6	330724	1.2	285107	72	Agristat (2022)
Linum usitatissimum (extruded)	6	10.2	9.6	10.5	1.6	874186	1.2	728488	184	Diepenbrock and Pörksen (1992); Mirzaie et al. (2020); Swiss granum (2022)
Linum usitatissimum (oil)	8	17.7	16.0	4.1	0.6	338918	0.8	423647	107	Diepenbrock and Pörksen (1992); Mirzaie et al. (2020); Swiss granum (2022)
Lotus sp.	6	7.9	13.4	97.5	14.6	8087916	10.0	808792	133 *	Bullard and Crawford (1995); Elgersma et al. (2015); Hunt et al. (2015); MacAdam and Griggs (2013); Minneé et al. (2007); Özpinar et al. (2019)
Medicago sativa	6	0.0	21.3	78.5	11.8	6509044	13.0	500696	83 *	Bundesamt für Landwirtschaft (2016); Lfl. Institut für Pflanzenbau und Pflanzenzüchtung (2016); Suter and Frick (2022)
Multispecies pastures containing tannin rich species	4	2	18.3	93.3	14.0	7739513	10.0	773951	128 *	Grace et al. (2019); Jonker et al. (2019); Moloney et al. (2020)
Onobrychis sp.	5	7.8	6.6	86.0	12.9	7133957	9.0	792662	131 *	Agridea (2012); Malisch et al. (2017)
Origanum vulgare (leaves)	5	11.4	19.0	1.6	0.2	134161	3.0	44720	11	Baranauskiene et al. (2013); Dordas (2009); Rey et al. (2002); Sotiropoulou and Karamanos (2010)
Trifolium pratense	4	2.5	7.4	75.5	11.3	6259096	11.5	544269	90 *	Bundesamt für Landwirtschaft (2016)
Trifolium repens	4	2.0	12.8	75.9	11.4	6298971	8.0	787371	130 *	Bundesamt für Landwirtschaft (2016)
Vitis vinifera (grape marc)	3	14.4	6.4	26.9	4.0	2229858	1.0	2322768	587	Spinei and Oroian (2021); Taylor et al. (2005)
Zea mays (silage)	14	6.0	5.9	53.4	8.0	4430760	20.0	221538	56	Baux (2013)

Sheep

(continued on next page)

Table 2 (continued)

Product	Number of studies included	Mean reduction CH ₄ per g/kg DMI	±SD	Mean inclusion rate in ration reported in these studies	Daily required amount per head	Annual amount required for entire Swiss population	Estimated annual yield of product in CH	Area required to grow product for entire Swiss population	Swiss arable or grassland* area required to grow product for entire population	References for yield estimate
		%	%	DM %	DM kg/day	DM t/year	DM t/ha	ha	%	
Brassica napus (forage)	3	20.6	8.0	100.0	1.5	188082	5.0	37616	10	Keogh et al. (2012);Sala et al. (2008)
Cichorium intybus	4	5.5	4.4	89.6	1.3	168490	8.0	21061	3 *	Lee et al. (2015);Li and Kemp (2005)
Lotus sp.	3	41.0	18.6	100.0	1.5	188082	10.0	18808	3 *	Bullard and Crawford (1995); Elgersma et al. (2015);Hunt et al. (2015);MacAdam and Griggs (2013);Minneé et al. (2007);Özpınar et al. (2019)
Trifolium pratense	3	3.2	14.2	70.8	1.1	133224	11.5	11585	2 *	Bundesamt für Landwirtschaft (2016)
Trifolium repens	4	-10.4	12.4	80.4	1.2	151171	8.0	18896	3 *	Bundesamt für Landwirtschaft (2016)
DDGS (in cattle)	6	0.5	12.9	18.3	2.7	1516283	32850			Furrer and Grüter (2020)

^a The table only includes products identified during the literature research, for which at least three independent publications were available. The inclusion rate of the product in the animal's diet is based on an average from the publications on which the average reduction in CH₄ is based. Required amounts on a population level are calculated based on 1.52 mio head of cattle and 0.34 mio sheep kept in Switzerland (CH) in 2020 (Bundesamt für Statistik, 2021). The average yields of the products and the current production in CH were estimated based on references given in the last column. The percentage of agricultural area required to grow sufficient product for the entire cattle and sheep population was based on the total arable area in CH for arable cultures (0.39 mio ha), or for pasture plants for the current area of pastures and meadows (0.61 mio ha, indicated with *) (Bundesamt für Statistik, 2021). Cells, where no information was available are denoted with NA.

(where applicable), CH₄ emission in g/kg DMI, and where available in g/kg milk, or in g/kg average daily gain (ADG). In most studies, these variables were extracted directly from the results section but in certain cases they were calculated based on the information given as CH₄ emission in g/d and daily DMI, milk yield or ADG. The data from all publications were checked twice for correctness. 96% of the included studies listed in Table 1 were published after the year 2000. Fig. 2 illustrates in which countries the experiments included in further analyses were conducted.

Interventions were assigned to one of two concepts: 1) Product based interventions aimed at changing the composition of the animal's diet by introducing other feedstuffs or changing their ratio, 2) Process based interventions, relying on different management processes, such as grazing management, harvest date, or conservation of feedstuffs.

In order to assess the variability of the effect size of certain interventions, publications evaluating the same intervention were grouped. For process-based interventions, publications were grouped based on the nutritional strategy proposed to reduce CH₄ production (e.g. decreasing forage maturity or increasing grazing pressure). If several experiments were carried out evaluating the same intervention within one publication, the effect size was averaged over all trials to create one value per publication. If different treatments were investigated within the same publication, effect size was averaged within treatment.

As the impact of feeding interventions was found to differ between ruminant species (van Gastelen et al., 2019) their effectiveness was calculated separately for cattle and sheep. For determination of effectiveness of individual feeding interventions, products or processes that had been investigated in the same species in at least three independent publications were considered. The effect size of these interventions was expressed in percent reduction (or increase) in CH₄ in g/kg DMI, milk or ADG using the following formula:

$$([\text{CH}_4 \text{ in g/kg on control diet}] - [\text{CH}_4 \text{ in g/kg on intervention}]) / [\text{CH}_4 \text{ in g/kg on control diet}] * 100$$

Data were plotted in R Studio (version 3.6.1) using the packages *ggplot* and *beeswarm*.

2.2. Assessing the land-requirements of selected product-based feeding interventions

For the selected products where three independent publications were available to calculate a mean reduction in CH₄ g/kg DMI, the area required to grow the product was assessed. Products were not included in this analysis if they were an extract (e.g. an essential oil or a specific plant component, where no information was given on the amount of crude plant material required to produce it) or if they were unspecific (e.g. increase in feeding mixed concentrates). For the selected products, the average required daily intake (in % DMI) was calculated based on the publications assessing their effectiveness as a CH₄ inhibitor. In order to assess if these product-based interventions could be implemented for the entire population of cattle or sheep kept in Switzerland, the required daily percentage in DMI of each product was extrapolated based on an average feed intake per head (15 kg DM/d in cattle, 1.5 kg DM/d in sheep, estimated based on Agroscope, 2021; Bundesanstalt für Agrarwirtschaft und Bergbauernfragen, 2023; Steinwidder et al., 2007) and animal numbers in 2020: 1.52 Mio head of cattle and 0.34 Mio head of sheep (Bundesamt für Statistik, 2021). Based on these assumptions, it was calculated how much product would be required nationally on an annual basis (t DM per year). To evaluate, if the required amount could be met by the current Swiss production, a literature research was carried out to establish a potential average annual yield of the crop. All plants included in this research are currently grown in Switzerland, but the number of publications reporting national yields of the plants of interest was limited. Therefore, publications reporting yields from other temperate countries were also considered. Where several publications on the yield were available, we chose an average value within the range reported in these studies. Based on these yield estimates, we calculated how much area would be required to grow this amount of produce. For

Fig. 3. Histogram of the number of animals used per treatment group in the selected publications.

arable cultures, the required area was then set into relation to the current arable area of Switzerland (0.4 mio ha). For cultures, which could be established on pasture and which made up the entire ration of the ruminants in the assessed studies, the area was set into relation with the current Swiss area consisting of pastures and meadows (0.6 mio ha). All references referring to effectiveness and yields of the selected feeding interventions are cited in Table 2.

3. Results

3.1. Dataset and effectiveness of feeding interventions

The literature search resulted in a cattle dataset of 137 publications providing data on CH₄ in g/kg DMI (Table 1). Of these publications, 79 further provided data on CH₄ in g/kg milk, and 24 on CH₄ in g/kg ADG. The sheep dataset was based on 47 publications for CH₄ in g/kg DMI, 2 of which further provided data on CH₄ in g/kg ADG (none provided CH₄ in g/kg milk). On average, the number of animals used within a treatment group to test the effect of an intervention was (mean ± standard deviation) 10 ± 8 individuals for cattle and 8 ± 4 individuals for sheep (Fig. 3).

On the control diets, which varied considerably between studies (e.g. TMR with 40% concentrates vs completely grass-based diet), the mean CH₄ emission (averaged within publications) was 22.6 ± 5.6 g/kg DMI, 17.6 ± 5.6 g/kg milk and 223 ± 138 g/kg ADG for cattle. For sheep, the average CH₄ emission on the control diet was 21.6 ± 5.2 g/kg DMI and 317 ± 233 g/kg ADG (note that ADG in sheep was only available from 2 publications). For cattle, the average reduction in CH₄ emissions (over all interventions and publications) achieved by the intervention treatments compared to the control treatment was 7.4 ± 11.5% for g/kg DMI, 8.5 ± 11.0% for g/kg milk and 13.3 ± 27.1% for g/kg ADG. In sheep, the average reduction in CH₄ was 8.2 ± 16.6% in g/kg DMI and 6.4 ± 51.1% in g/kg ADG. The range of the data is illustrated in Fig. 4 A-C.

Table 1 lists the plant species, products and processes investigated in publications included in the overall database. The most common product-based interventions tested in cattle were the replacement of grass-based roughage with legume forages or tannin-containing plants, an increase in content of concentrate or maize silage in the ration, supplementation of oilseeds (linseed, rapeseed, sunflower), plant-based oils, essential oils, or other extracts. In sheep, similar approaches were investigated, although most studies focused on forage-based interventions. The most frequently investigated processes were related to pasture and forage management, such as decreasing forage maturity, or increasing the animals' intake. For a large proportion of the studies included in the literature review, only one or two publications were found to investigate the same feeding intervention in the same ruminant species.

Effect sizes of selected individual product-based interventions to reduce CH₄ in g/kg DMI are shown in Figs. 5 and 6. These figures include interventions which had been studied in at least three independent publications in the respective species. In numerous interventions, the effect of the product differed drastically between studies using different or even the same control diets. For eleven out of the 17 selected feedstuffs assessed in cattle, there was a discrepancy in the effect, i.e. at least one study reported an increase in CH₄ in g/kg DMI while at least one other publication reported a decrease. The same was the case for three out of the seven selected feedstuffs in sheep. These interventions are those that have datapoints below 0 in Figs. 5 and 6. The effect averaged over the selected studies showed a reduction in CH₄ in g/kg DMI for 15 of the 17 product-based interventions in cattle and five out of six in sheep. The highest

Fig. 4. Illustration of the range of all included literature data on CH₄ emission by cattle and sheep in g/kg DMI (A), g/kg milk (B) and g/kg ADG (C). In each of the selected publications, the emission of the animals was quantified in a control treatment (red) and at least one intervention (blue). Note that none of the included publications reported data on milk yield for sheep, and that sheep data in Fig. C are based on two publications only. Boxplots indicate median, as well as 25% and 75% quartiles.

Fig. 5. Effectiveness of product-based feeding interventions in cattle expressed as percentage reduction in CH₄ in g/kg DMI. Individual dots represent the average effect of an intervention within one study. Boxplots indicate median, as well as 25% and 75% quartiles. The grey dash indicates the mean.

Fig. 6. Effectiveness of product-based feeding interventions in sheep expressed as percentage reduction in CH₄ in g/kg DMI. Individual dots represent the average effect of an intervention within one study. Boxplots indicate median, as well as 25% and 75% quartiles. The grey dash indicates the mean.

average effects with a consistent reduction in CH₄ in g/kg DMI in cattle were found for the feeding of rape oil (15%), sunflower oil (20%), linseed oil (18%) and grape marc (14%). The feeding of linseed and oregano leaves showed an average reduction in CH₄ in g/kg DMI above 10%, but for both products, there were studies reporting no effect or an increase in CH₄ in g/kg DMI. In sheep, the feeding of *Brassica napus* fodder and *Lotus sp.* resulted in the highest average reductions in CH₄ in g/kg DMI of 21% and 41% respectively. Several interventions were investigated in both species: the supplementation or increase in concentrates, the feeding of *Lotus sp.*, *Trifolium pratense* and *Trifolium repens*. The supplementation of concentrates and the feeding of *Trifolium pratense* show a similar reduction in CH₄ in g/kg DMI in both species of approximately 10% and 3%, respectively. The reduction in CH₄ in g/kg DMI when feeding *Lotus sp.* was considerably higher in sheep than in cattle (41% vs 8%). The effect of feeding *T. repens* was low in cattle and even adverse in sheep (2% vs -10%).

For eleven of the selected products for cattle, there were at least three publications available to assess the efficacy with regard to CH₄ in g/kg milk (Fig. 7A). With regard to the effect on in CH₄ in g/kg ADG there were three publications assessing the effect of supplementing or increasing the amount of concentrates in the diet (Fig. 7B). The plots indicate that products, which show a reduction in CH₄ in g/kg DMI in cattle also show a reduction in CH₄ in g/kg milk or ADG, except for multispecies pastures, where on average CH₄ in g/kg milk was increased.

With regard to the selected process-based interventions in cattle (Fig. 8A), two of them showed a reduction of CH₄ in g/kg DMI in all studies: an increase in grazing pressure and an increase in maize maturity. For sheep (Fig. 8B), an increase in intake was associated with a reduction in CH₄ in g/kg DMI in all assessed studies. The effect of the remaining processes showed a discrepancy between

Fig. 7. Effectiveness of product-based feeding interventions in cattle, where at least three studies were available to assess the effect on CH₄ in g/kg milk (A) and CH₄ in g/kg ADG (B). For sheep neither variable was assessed at least three times for the same product. Individual dots represent the average effect of an intervention within one study. Boxplots indicate median, as well as 25% and 75% quartiles. The grey dash indicates the mean.

Fig. 8. Effectiveness of process-based feeding interventions in cattle (A) and sheep (B) expressed as percentage reduction in CH₄ in g/kg DMI (note the difference in scale). Individual dots represent the average effect of an intervention within one study. Boxplots indicate median, as well as 25% and 75% quartiles. The grey dash indicates the mean.

studies. The average effect of an increase in intake was higher and consistent in sheep when compared to cattle (11% vs 2%). In cattle, decreasing the maturity of cut forage or pasture showed a reduction in CH₄ in g/kg milk (Fig. 9A). Increasing grazing pressure was associated with an increase in CH₄ in g/kg ADG (Fig. 9B).

In terms of magnitude, some processes are comparable with the reduction found for certain product-based interventions: with an average reduction in CH₄ in g/kg DMI of 19%, an increase in grazing pressure shows a similar efficacy in cattle as the supplementation with sunflower oil or linseed oil. A 7% reduction achieved by the increase in maize maturity in cattle is comparable to the supplementation with *Lotus sp.*, *Onobrychis sp.* or maize silage. In sheep, the reduction achieved by an increased intake is lower than the effect of the supplementation of *Lotus sp.* or *Brassica napus* fodder, but higher than the effect of feeding *Cichorium intybius* (6%).

3.2. Land requirements of selected product-based feeding interventions

The product-based feeding interventions selected for this analysis are listed in Table 2. The required areas in order to supply the entire Swiss populations of cattle (dairy and beef) and sheep with amounts sufficient to realize the average effect size in CH₄ mitigation

Fig. 9. Effectiveness of process-based feeding interventions in cattle, where at least three studies were available to assess the effect on CH₄ in g/kg milk (A) and CH₄ in g/kg ADG (B). For sheep neither variable was assessed at least three times for the same product. Individual dots represent the average effect of an intervention within one study. Boxplots indicate median, as well as 25% and 75% quartiles. The grey dash indicates the mean.

are presented in Table 2. Yields and area estimates should be interpreted with care, as they are (realistic) estimates. For nine interventions, the entire Swiss arable land or grassland would have to be used to grow the product in question, in order to reduce CH₄ emissions by a few percent. For cattle, the product which would require the least area is *Origanum* (11% of arable land). For sheep, the required areas are much smaller (below 10% of the land) than those for cattle, which can be explained by the smaller population and the lower DMI.

4. Discussion

During the past three decades, a broad spectrum of dietary interventions with various feed plants, often based on effects of specific plant metabolites like tannins or essential oils (Khiaosa-Ard and Zebeli, 2013; Vasta et al., 2019) was investigated for their ruminal CH₄ mitigation potential. These plant additives have repeatedly shown the potential to mitigate CH₄ production *in vitro*, but fewer studies have investigated their effect *in vivo*, where their impact on enteric CH₄ production is often more variable and less pronounced (Jayanegara et al., 2012). However, some options of mitigating enteric CH₄ production with forage plants and herbs were identified after *in vivo* investigations, and are referred to in recent reviews (Arndt et al., 2022; Min et al., 2020; Varga et al., 2022). Often, such products are claimed to be more natural, since they are not synthetic, and sustainable, since they are (erroneously) considered to be non-arable crops. Additionally, in the case of herbs or leaves, several potentially beneficial effects on animal welfare and ecosystems are attributed to the production and dietary inclusion of such herbal feedstuffs (Gregorini et al., 2017; Leiber et al., 2020).

However, what has rarely been assessed and defined, are the resources and efforts required to produce the necessary amounts of such plants or their extracts in order to realize the desired effects in large (e.g. national) populations of ruminant livestock. Discussion about the size of arable surfaces to produce these plant materials is widely lacking, and the gap between experimental evidence and practical implementation is still wide. Therefore, proposals based on experimental findings often lack realistic in-practice potential. Since land-use is one of the most critical issues of global food production - and the feed-food competition is part of that problem (Schader et al., 2015) - it is of particular importance to deliver estimates for the land resources needed for proposed plant-based CH₄ mitigation measures. The land requirements in connection with estimated mitigation effects of proposed dietary interventions would provide a basis to assessing their overall suitability and sustainability.

The present study, based on the example of ruminant production systems in Switzerland, aims at opening the discussion on this

important aspect of CH₄ mitigation through feeding interventions. The area of agricultural land in Switzerland and the size of national cattle and sheep populations were used to estimate the potential effects and necessary land resources of scientifically proposed dietary interventions. With its specificity of a small arable to grassland proportion (38:62) (Bundesamt für Statistik, 2021), Switzerland is not representative for intensive agricultural countries in Europe, but it well represents grassland-based ruminant production systems (Hofstetter et al., 2014). In any case, the estimates developed in this study highlight that required resources for plant-based CH₄ mitigators are not negligible.

4.1. Effect sizes of plant-based methane mitigation interventions

With regard to the large body of literature considering plant-based feed additives with CH₄ mitigation potential (Durmic et al., 2014; Jayanegara et al., 2012; Min et al., 2020; Ugbohu et al., 2019; Varga et al., 2022; Vasta et al., 2019), the number of interventions investigated with at least three *in vivo* studies was rather small. One considerable reason was, that we restricted selection to plants with potential to grow in temperate climatic regions, while experimental research also includes various tropical plants (Durmic et al., 2022; Soliva et al., 2008; Varga et al., 2022). Furthermore, large parts of the literature evaluating and discussing the topic still rely on *in vitro* data (Durmic et al., 2022; Jayanegara et al., 2012; Varga et al., 2022).

Of the interventions covered by our selection criteria the averaged effects for CH₄ mitigation (related to DM intake) in cattle and sheep were around 7–8%, with large standard deviations and a considerable number of studies, where the intervention resulted in an increase in CH₄. This overall picture is congruent with the review of Vargas et al. (2022) who also found high numbers of studies on CH₄ mitigators in grassland-based systems with no effect or even increases. The only additives for cattle achieving aspired effects in all studies were oils (rapeseed, sunflower, linseed) and grape marc. In sheep, it was fodder rape, trefoil (*Lotus sp.*), *Cichorium intybus*, as well as the supplementation with mixed concentrates. Notably, with few of these additives the effects were not just consistent but even at around 20% (cattle) or 40% (sheep) reduction of CH₄ emissions per unit of DMI. However, for most products the effect on CH₄ mitigation varied considerably between studies. This variation may be caused by differences in study design, animal breed, control diets or measurement methods between publications. Therefore, the average effect size calculated in this study is a somewhat theoretical value, which does not reflect a specific production system. However, this problem reflects the very small basis of available *in vivo* study data.

4.2. Land requirements of plant-based methane mitigation interventions

The subsequent objective of this study was to assess, if the daily supplementation of the entire national population of cattle and sheep would be feasible based on the area of arable land or, in the case of pasture plants, grassland in Switzerland, considering the country as a model for grassland-based production regions (Huber et al., 2022). The calculations shown in Table 2 allow a basic assessment of the land which would be required for the growth of the selected plant products intended for methane mitigation. Although the yields and areas are based on realistic estimates from literature, the numbers should be interpreted with care. Furthermore, climate change is likely to affect the future yields and demand for these products. On one hand, plants thriving under warm conditions (e.g. trefoil or sainfoin), may become more suitable for cultivation in Switzerland. On the other hand, increasing temperatures and drought may make it increasingly difficult to keep ruminant livestock on lowland pastures, resulting in a reduction in animal numbers and consequently the required amounts of plant material. As the effect of climate change on Swiss agriculture is hard to predict, making assumptions on yields, required amounts and animal numbers is somewhat speculative. However, the calculations shown in Table 2 help to put the efforts which would have to go into methane mitigation through these feeding interventions into perspective. They indicate, that several plant-based products assessed in cattle would require an area larger than the total of current Swiss arable land or grassland, in order to be available at the amounts necessary to achieve the methane mitigation effects from experimental literature. For example, if the most effective product – sunflower oil – would be produced at the required amount within the country, its production would require over 2/3rd of the area currently used for the production of arable crops. Other effective plant-based oils would require an area even larger and the production of grape marc for all Swiss cattle (which is notably a by-product and thus a desirable feed stuff) would require an area almost six times larger than the current national arable area. Even the comparably small area required to grow *Origanum sp.* (10% of arable area) still exceeds the areas currently used to grow e.g. potatoes and vegetables (3% of arable land each), sugar beets (4%), or barley (7%) (Bundesamt für Statistik, 2021) – cultures which are of importance for the supply of local food and feed. This example illustrates a conflict in land use, in particular if CH₄ mitigation is given priority over national food security. Even for the comparatively simple example of maize silage, which is already a standard component in most dairy rations, the increase in land use would be 5-fold: from 11% of arable land at the moment (Bundesamt für Statistik, 2021) to 56% if the inclusion rate of 534 g/kg DM is to be met.

For sheep, the implementation of the assessed feedstuffs for the national population appears somewhat more feasible, as growing them would only require 10% percent of the arable land (for *Brassica napus* fodder) or 2–3% of grassland. However, considering the areas of arable land currently used for food production, these proportions are still substantial.

The integration of effective pasture plants into the seed mixtures for forage production could be more practical than the supplementation of specific additives or concentrates. The integration of these plants into existing pastures requires no change in land use, does thus not create a conflict between CH₄ mitigation and food security, and the pasture plants are directly consumed by the animals. In contrast to other feed supplements, their administration is less labor intensive. Species like chicory, sainfoin, red clover or trefoil can be integrated in existing pastures and meadows to create multispecies swards, which have also been linked with a wide array of ecological and agricultural benefits (Bryant et al., 2017; Isbell et al., 2015; Lüscher et al., 2022). However, the dietary inclusion rate of

most pasture plants assessed in the studies included in this review was very high (up to 100%). Due to their reduced yield, establishing monocultures of the pasture plants in question, e.g. red clover (*Trifolium repens* or *T. pratense*), sainfoin (*Onobrychis* sp.), alfalfa (*Medicago sativa*) or trefoil (*Lotus* sp.) would require an area exceeding the current Swiss grassland area. Furthermore, seasonal availability of the plants would make year-round administration challenging and pure legume pastures would be an unbalanced diet for grazer-type ruminant species like cattle and sheep. While the integration of effective pasture plants into existing pastures requires comparably little effort, it remains unclear if a small inclusion rate would have any notable effect on CH₄ emission. This is reflected by the comparatively low efficacy (and its variability) of multispecies swards reported in the studies included in this review. Furthermore, when compared to a control diet, feeding on multispecies swards resulted in an average increase in CH₄ per kg milk in the studies included in this review (Fig. 7A), indicating that a lower feed efficiency of these diets may result in increased emissions to achieve the same milk yield. This example illustrates that – beyond efficacy of a mitigator and the land required to produce it – a multitude of aspects have to be considered when assessing if a feeding intervention can be realized on farm.

The proportional land distribution of Switzerland makes the examples discussed above rather drastic, but it generally shows that plant-based feed additives for CH₄ mitigation would require agricultural areas large enough to evoke debates around land-use, such as the challenge of feed-food competition (Schader et al., 2015; Wilkinson, 2011). Since land-use change relates to carbon sequestration and release (Yumashev et al., 2022), such measures need to undergo thorough climate impact analyses for the production side, before they can be reasonably proposed as measures to mitigate ruminal methanogenesis. Furthermore, the target of grassland-based ruminant production, which is particularly tailored for regions with small resources of arable land (Leiber, 2022) becomes obsolete if the inhibition of CH₄ requires additional agricultural area.

The effect size of the assessed process-based interventions was highly variable and it was not assessed, which additional efforts would be required to realize them in terms of labour, costs, or land-use. However, the results highlight, that certain processes related to pasture management and feed production may be as efficient as product-based interventions. For example, an increase in maize maturity is as efficient in reducing CH₄ per unit DMI as an increase in maize proportions in the ration of cattle (7% vs. 6%). An increase in grazing pressure in cattle appears as effective as the supplementation with linseed oil. Both examples highlight, that the improvement of management practices in existing systems may be a more sensible way to achieve CH₄ mitigation than the implementation of certain feedstuffs.

4.3. Methodological aspects

Besides the effect size and feasibility, the existing data also have to be critically discussed with regard to methodology of the research done until now. The results of our literature review illustrate the sheer amount of combinations of feeding interventions and control treatments which have been investigated to date. Few studies have replicated previously investigated combinations of product and control treatment and if so, the results often vary considerably between such studies. For example, the comparison between alfalfa and grass was investigated in at least five studies in cattle, but the results vary from a 40% increase in emissions to a 20% decrease. In the case of concentrate supplementation, a reduction in CH₄ in kg/DMI ranges from 0% to almost 40%. These examples and the variability of effects as displayed in Figs. 5 to 7 illustrate, that the investigation of product-control-combinations require manifold independent replications to acquire certainty about the effectiveness of the intervention and knowledge about the variability of the effects under real practice conditions. Rather than investigating ever new feed additives and components, research projects verifying existing studies would be just as valuable. In particular, because it is rarely possible to investigate more than ten individual animals in one study.

The data further demonstrate, that defining the control diet is as important as the intervention itself. Sainfoin compared to alfalfa resulted in hardly any reduction in CH₄ in kg/DMI, while sainfoin compared to grass showed a considerable reduction of approx. 15%. This should also be considered when suggesting interventions on farm level: compared to a low-quality pasture, feeding white clover may decrease emissions, but compared to a nutritious rye-grass pasture, the effect may be negligible. Due to the very low number of studies repeating the same intervention under different conditions, it is almost impossible to generalize effects or to allocate them systematically to different production conditions.

The dataset may further be skewed by a positive-results bias, where studies showing the desired effect of the intervention, i.e. a reduction in CH₄, may be more frequently submitted or published than studies finding no effect or even an increase in CH₄. Given the variability of the results in the literature dataset, it is likely that the inclusion of each new publication may completely change the average effect size of an intervention.

5. Conclusion

The present review aimed to relate potential effects of plant-based CH₄ inhibitors with the land requirements for implementation. Based on the criterion, that for a certain plant-based intervention at least three published *in vivo* studies were available, the number of options was surprisingly small. On average, effect-sizes are below 10% reduction of CH₄ per unit of DM intake, with high variation between studies, including adverse results. Production of the necessary amounts of such feed additives would require considerable amounts of agricultural area, a fact which has been widely neglected, so far. Since land requirements imply climate change threats as well, our study results in an urgent call for assessing carbon-cycle effects by production of the debated plant-based CH₄ inhibitors. In terms of feeding interventions, the integration of plants with inhibitory effects into artificial or natural swards appears to be the most practicable solution, which requires no change in land use, bears little risks and has other beneficial effects.

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CRediT authorship contribution statement

Marie Dittmann: Investigation, Formal analysis, Data curation, Visualization, Writing – original draft, Writing – review & editing.
Florian Leiber: Conceptualization, Investigation, Writing – original draft, Writing – review & editing.

Declaration of Competing Interest

The authors declare no competing interests.

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References

- Aboagye, I.A., Oba, M., Koenig, K.M., Zhao, G.Y., Beauchemin, K.A., 2019. Use of gallic acid and hydrolyzable tannins to reduce methane emission and nitrogen excretion in beef cattle fed a diet containing alfalfa silage. *J. Anim. Sci.* 97 (5), 2230–2244.
- Agridea. (2012). Esparssette reich an kondensierten Tanninen. Agridea. (https://www.esparssette.ch/fileadmin/esparssette/documents/Merkblatt_Esparssetteanbau_Agridea_D.pdf), accessed: May 1st, 2023.
- Agristat. (2022). Statistische Erhebungen und Schätzungen über Landwirtschaft und Ernährung 2021 (p. Kapitel 2, Pflanzenbau). Schweizer Bauernverband, Agristat.
- Agroscope. (2021). Fütterungsempfehlungen für Wiederkäuer (Grünes Buch). (www.agroscope.ch/gruenes-buch), accessed: May 1st, 2023.
- Aguerre, M.J., Wattiaux, M.A., Powell, J.M., Broderick, G.A., Arndt, C., 2011. Effect of forage-to-concentrate ratio in dairy cow diets on emission of methane, carbon dioxide, and ammonia, lactation performance, and manure excretion. *J. Dairy Sci.* 94 (6), 3081–3093. <https://doi.org/10.3168/jds.2010-4011>.
- Alemu, A.W., Romero-Pérez, A., Araujo, R.C., Beauchemin, K.A., 2019. Effect of reencapsulated nitrate and microencapsulated blend of essential oils on growth performance and methane emissions from beef steers fed backgrounding diets. *Animals* 9 (1), 1–19. <https://doi.org/10.3390/ani9010021>.
- Amaral, G.A., David, D.B., Gere, J.I., Savian, J.V., Kohmann, M.M., Nadin, L.B., Chopra, F.S., Bayer, C., Carvalho, P.C.F., 2016. Methane emissions from sheep grazing pearl millet (*Penisetum americanum* (L.) Leeke) swards fertilized with increasing nitrogen levels. *Small Rumin. Res.* 141, 118–123. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.smallrumres.2016.07.011>.
- Archimède, H., Rira, M., Eugène, M., Fleury, J., Lastel, M.L., Pericarpin, F., Silou-Etienne, T., Morgavi, D.P., Doreau, M., 2018. Intake, total-tract digestibility and methane emissions of Texel and Blackbelly sheep fed C4 and C3 grasses tested simultaneously in a temperate and a tropical area. *J. Clean. Prod.* 185, 455–463. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jclepro.2018.03.059>.
- Arndt, C., Hristov, A.N., Price, W.J., McClelland, S.C., Pelaez, A.M., Cueva, S.F., Oh, J., Dijkstra, J., Bannink, A., Bayat, A.R., Crompton, L.A., Eugène, M.A., Enahoro, D., Kebreab, E., Kreuzer, M., McGee, M., Martin, C., Newbold, C.J., Reynolds, C.K., Yu, Z., 2022. Full adoption of the most effective strategies to mitigate methane emissions by ruminants can help meet the 1.5 °C target by 2030 but not 2050. *Proc. Natl. Acad. Sci. USA* 119 (20), 1–10. <https://doi.org/10.1073/pnas.2111294119>.
- Baranauskienė, R., Venskutonis, P.R., Dambrauskienė, E., Viskelis, P., 2013. Harvesting time influences the yield and oil composition of *Origanum vulgare* L. ssp. *vulgare* and ssp. *hirtum*. *Ind. Crops Prod.* 49, 43–51. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.indcrop.2013.04.024>.
- Barbero, R.P., Malheiros, E.B., Araújo, T.L.R., Nave, R.L.G., Mulliniks, J.T., Berchielli, T.T., Ruggieri, A.C., Reis, R.A., 2015. Combining Marandu grass grazing height and supplementation level to optimize growth and productivity of yearling bulls. *Anim. Feed Sci. Technol.* 209, 110–118. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.anifeedsci.2015.09.010>.
- Baux, A., 2013. Zwanzig Jahre Sortenversuche mit Silomais in der Schweiz. *Agrar. Schweiz* 4 (7–8), 330–337.
- Bayat, A.R., Ventto, L., Kairenius, P., Stefanski, T., Leskinen, H., Tapio, I., Negussie, E., Vilkki, J., Shingfield, K.J., 2017. Dietary forage to concentrate ratio and sunflower oil supplement alter rumen fermentation, ruminal methane emissions, and nutrient utilization in lactating cows. *Transl. Anim. Sci.* 1 (3), 277–286. <https://doi.org/10.2527/tas2017.0032>.
- Bayat, A.R., Tapio, I., Vilkki, J., Shingfield, K.J., Leskinen, H., 2018. Plant oil supplements reduce methane emissions and improve milk fatty acid composition in dairy cows fed grass silage-based diets without affecting milk yield. *J. Dairy Sci.* 101 (2), 1136–1151. <https://doi.org/10.3168/jds.2017-13545>.
- Beauchemin, K.A., McGinn, S.M., 2006. Methane emissions from beef cattle: effects of fumaric acid, essential oil, and canola oil. *J. Anim. Sci.* 84 (6), 1489–1496. <https://doi.org/10.2527/2006.8461489x>.
- Beauchemin, K.A., McGinn, S.M., Petit, H.V., 2007. Methane abatement strategies for cattle: lipid supplementation of diets. *Can. J. Anim. Sci.* 87 (3), 431–440. <https://doi.org/10.4141/CJAS07011>.
- Beauchemin, K.A., Kreuzer, M., O'Mara, F., McAllister, T.A., 2008. Nutritional management for enteric methane abatement: a review. *Aust. J. Exp. Agric.* 48 (1–2), 21–27. <https://doi.org/10.1071/EA07199>.
- Beck, M.R., Thompson, L.R., Williams, G.D., Place, S.E., Gunter, S.A., Reuter, R.R., 2019. Fat supplements differing in physical form improve performance but divergently influence methane emissions of grazing beef cattle. *Anim. Feed Sci. Technol.* 254 (October 2018), 114210 <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.anifeedsci.2019.114210>.
- Benchaar, C., 2020. Feeding oregano oil and its main component carvacrol does not affect ruminal fermentation, nutrient utilization, methane emissions, milk production, or milk fatty acid composition of dairy cows. *J. Dairy Sci.* 103 (2), 1516–1527. <https://doi.org/10.3168/jds.2019-17230>.
- Benchaar, C., Hassanat, F., Gervais, R., Chouinard, P.Y., Julien, C., Petit, H.V., Massé, D.I., 2013. Effects of increasing amounts of corn dried distillers grains with solubles in dairy cow diets on methane production, ruminal fermentation, digestion, N balance, and milk production. *J. Dairy Sci.* 96 (4), 2413–2427. <https://doi.org/10.3168/jds.2012-6037>.
- Benchaar, C., Hassanat, F., Gervais, R., Chouinard, P.Y., Petit, H.V., Massé, D.I., 2014. Methane production, digestion, ruminal fermentation, nitrogen balance, and milk production of cows fed corn silage- or barley silage-based diets. *J. Dairy Sci.* 97 (2), 961–974. <https://doi.org/10.3168/jds.2013-7122>.
- Benchaar, C., Hassanat, F., Martineau, R., Gervais, R., 2015. Linseed oil supplementation to dairy cows fed diets based on red clover silage or corn silage: effects on methane production, rumen fermentation, nutrient digestibility, N balance, and milk production. *J. Dairy Sci.* 98 (11), 7993–8008. <https://doi.org/10.3168/jds.2015-9398>.
- Bernier, J.N., Undi, M., Plaizier, J.C., Wittenberg, K.M., Donohoe, G.R., Ominski, K.H., 2012. Impact of prolonged cold exposure on dry matter intake and enteric methane emissions of beef cows overwintered on low-quality forage diets with and without supplemented wheat and corn dried distillers' grain with solubles. *Can. J. Anim. Sci.* 92 (4), 493–500. <https://doi.org/10.4141/CJAS2012-040>.

- Boadi, D.A., Wittenberg, K.M., 2002. Methane production from dairy and beef heifers fed forages differing in nutrient density using the sulphur hexafluoride (SF₆) tracer gas technique. *Can. J. Anim. Sci.* 82 (2), 201–206. <https://doi.org/10.4141/A01-017>.
- Boland, T.M., Quinlan, C., Pierce, K.M., Lynch, M.B., Kenny, D.A., Kelly, A.K., Purcell, P.J., 2013. The effect of pasture pregrazing herbage mass on methane emissions, ruminal fermentation, and average daily gain of grazing beef heifers. *J. Anim. Sci.* 91 (8), 3867–3874. <https://doi.org/10.2527/jas.2013-5900>.
- Boland, T.M., Pierce, K.M., Kelly, A.K., Kenny, D.A., Lynch, M.B., Waters, S.M., Whelan, S.J., McKay, Z.C., 2020. Feed intake, methane emissions, milk production and rumen methanogen populations of grazing dairy cows supplemented with various C 18 fatty acid sources. *Animals* 10 (12), 2380. <https://doi.org/10.3390/ani10122380>.
- Bouchard, K., Wittenberg, K.M., Legesse, G., Krause, D.O., Khafipour, E., Buckley, K.E., Ominski, K.H., 2015. Comparison of feed intake, body weight gain, enteric methane emission and relative abundance of rumen microbes in steers fed sainfoin and lucerne silages under western Canadian conditions. *Grass Forage Sci.* 70 (1), 116–129. <https://doi.org/10.1111/gfs.12105>.
- Brask, M., Lund, P., Hellwing, A.L.F., Poulsen, M., Weisbjerg, M.R., 2013. Enteric methane production, digestibility and rumen fermentation in dairy cows fed different forages with and without rapeseed fat supplementation. *Anim. Feed Sci. Technol.* 184 (1–4), 67–79. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.anifeedsci.2013.06.006>.
- Bryant, R.H., Miller, M.E., Greenwood, S.L., Edwards, G.R., 2017. Milk yield and nitrogen excretion of dairy cows grazing binary and multispecies pastures. *Grass Forage Sci.* 72 (4), 806–817. <https://doi.org/10.1111/gfs.12274>.
- Bullard, M.J., Crawford, T.J., 1995. Productivity of Lotus corniculatus L. (bird's-foot trefoil) in the UK when grown under low-input conditions as spaced plants, monoculture swards or mixed swards. *Grass Forage Sci.* 50, 439–446. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1365-2494.1995.tb02338.x>.
- Bundesamt für Landwirtschaft. (2016). Sorten, Saat- und Pflanzgut in der Schweiz. https://www.blw.admin.ch/dam/blw/de/dokumente/Markt/Einfuhr_von_Agrarprodukten/Saatgetreide_und_Saemereien/PublSorten.pdf.download.pdf/PublSorten_Saat_Pflanzgut_dt.pdf, accessed: May 1st, 2023.
- Bundesamt für Statistik. (2021). *Landwirtschaftliche Strukturerhebung*. (<https://www.bfs.admin.ch/bfs/de/home/statistiken/land-forstwirtschaft/landwirtschaft.html>), accessed: May 1st, 2023.
- Bundesanstalt für Agrarwirtschaft und Bergbauernfragen. (2023). *IDB Deckungsbeiträge und Kalkulationsdaten*. (<https://idb.agrarforschung.at/>), accessed: May 1st, 2023.
- Caetano, M., Wilkes, M.J., Pitchford, W.S., Lee, S.J., Hynd, P.L., 2019. Effect of ensiled crimped grape marc on energy intake, performance and gas emissions of beef cattle. *Anim. Feed Sci. Technol.* 247 (October 2018), 166–172. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.anifeedsci.2018.10.007>.
- Carmona-Flores, L., Bionaz, M., Downing, T., Sahin, M., Cheng, L., Ates, S., 2020. Milk production, N partitioning, and methane emissions in dairy cows grazing mixed or spatially separated simple and diverse pastures. *Animals* 10 (8), 1301. <https://doi.org/10.3390/ani10081301>.
- Castro-Montoya, J., Peiren, N., Cone, J.W., Zweifel, B., Fievez, V., De Campeneere, S., 2015. In vivo and in vitro effects of a blend of essential oils on rumen methane mitigation. *Livest. Sci.* 180, 134–142. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.livsci.2015.08.010>.
- Chaves, A.V., Thompson, L.C., Iwaasa, A.D., Scott, S.L., Olson, M.E., Benchaar, C., Veira, D.M., McAllister, T.A., 2006. Effect of pasture type (alfalfa vs. grass) on methane and carbon dioxide production by yearling beef heifers. *Can. J. Anim. Sci.* 86 (3), 409–418. <https://doi.org/10.4141/A05-081>.
- Chen, D., Chen, X., Tu, Y., Wang, B., Lou, C., Ma, T., Diaio, Q., 2015. Effects of mulberry leaf flavonoid and resveratrol on methane emission and nutrient digestion in sheep. *Anim. Nutr.* 1 (4), 362–367. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.aninu.2015.12.008>.
- Cherif, C., Hassanat, F., Claveau, S., Girard, J., Gervais, R., Benchaar, C., 2018. Faba bean (*Vicia faba*) inclusion in dairy cow diets: Effect on nutrient digestion, rumen fermentation, nitrogen utilization, methane production, and milk performance. *J. Dairy Sci.* 101 (10), 8916–8928. <https://doi.org/10.3168/jds.2018-14890>.
- Chiavegato, M.B., Rowntree, J.E., Carmichael, D., Powers, W.J., 2015. Enteric methane from lactating beef cows managed with high-and low-input grazing systems. *J. Anim. Sci.* 93 (3), 1365–1375. <https://doi.org/10.2527/jas.2014-8128>.
- Chong, L., Zhuping, Z., Tongjun, G., Yongming, L., Hongmin, D., 2014. Changes in methane emission, rumen fermentation, and methanogenic community in response to silage and dry cornstall diets. *J. Basic Microbiol.* 54 (6), 521–530. <https://doi.org/10.1002/jobm.201200678>.
- Chung, Y.H., McGeough, E.J., Acharya, S., McAllister, T.A., McGinn, S.M., Harstad, O.M., Beauchemin, K.A., 2013. Enteric methane emission, diet digestibility, and nitrogen excretion from beef heifers fed sainfoin or alfalfa. *J. Anim. Sci.* 91 (10), 4861–4874. <https://doi.org/10.2527/jas.2013-6498>.
- Chuntrakort, P., Otsuka, M., Hayashi, K., Takenaka, A., Udchachon, S., Sommart, K., 2014. The effect of dietary coconut kernels, whole cottonseeds and sunflower seeds on the intake, digestibility and enteric methane emissions of Zebu beef cattle fed rice straw based diets. *Livest. Sci.* 161 (1), 80–89. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.livsci.2014.01.003>.
- Congio, G.F.S., Batalha, C.D.A., Chiavegato, M.B., Berndt, A., Oliveira, P.P.A., Frighetto, R.T.S., Maxwell, T.M.R., Gregorini, P., Da Silva, S.C., 2018. Strategic grazing management towards sustainable intensification at tropical pasture-based dairy systems. *Sci. Total Environ.* 636, 872–880. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.scitotenv.2018.04.301>.
- Dall-Orsoletta, A.C., Almeida, J.G.R., Carvalho, P.C.F., Savian, J.V., Ribeiro-Filho, H.M.N., 2016. Ryegrass pasture combined with partial total mixed ration reduces enteric methane emissions and maintains the performance of dairy cows during mid to late lactation. *J. Dairy Sci.* 99 (6), 4374–4383. <https://doi.org/10.3168/jds.2015-10396>.
- Dall-Orsoletta, A.C., Oziembowski, M.M., Berndt, A., Ribeiro-Filho, H.M.N., 2019. Enteric methane emission from grazing dairy cows receiving corn silage or ground corn supplementation. *Anim. Feed Sci. Technol.* 253 (August 2018), 65–73. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.anifeedsci.2019.05.009>.
- DeRamus, H.A., Clement, T.C., Giampola, D.D., Dickison, P.C., 2003. Methane emissions of beef cattle on forages. *J. Environ. Qual.* 32 (1), 269–277. <https://doi.org/10.2134/jeq2003.2690>.
- Diepenbrock, W., Pörksen, N., 1992. Effect of stand establishment and nitrogen fertilization on yield and yield physiology of linseed (*Linum usitatissimum* L.). *Ind. Crops Prod.* 1 (2–4), 165–173. [https://doi.org/10.1016/0926-6690\(92\)90015-N](https://doi.org/10.1016/0926-6690(92)90015-N).
- Dini, Y., Gere, J., Briano, C., Manetti, M., Juliarena, P., Picasso, V., Grattón, R., Astigarraga, L., 2012. Methane emission and milk production of dairy cows grazing pastures rich in legumes or rich in grasses in Uruguay. *Animals* 2 (2), 288–300. <https://doi.org/10.3390/ani2020288>.
- Dini, Y., Gere, J.I., Cajarville, C., Ciganda, V.S., 2018. Using highly nutritious pastures to mitigate enteric methane emissions from cattle grazing systems in South America. *Anim. Prod. Sci.* 58 (12), 2329–2334. <https://doi.org/10.1071/AN16803>.
- Dordas, C., 2009. Foliar application of calcium and magnesium improves growth, yield, and essential oil yield of oregano (*Origanum vulgare* ssp. *hirtum*). *Ind. Crops Prod.* 29 (2–3), 599–608. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.indcrop.2008.11.004>.
- Doreau, M., Ferlay, A., Rochette, Y., Martin, C., 2014. Effects of dehydrated lucerne and soya bean meal on milk production and composition, nutrient digestion, and methane and nitrogen losses in dairy cows receiving two different forages. *Animal* 8 (3), 420–430. <https://doi.org/10.1017/S1751731113002206>.
- Durmic, Z., Moate, P.J., Eckard, R., Revell, D.K., Williams, R., Vercoe, P.E., 2014. In vitro screening of selected feed additives, plant essential oils and plant extracts for rumen methane mitigation. *J. Sci. Food Agric.* 94 (6), 1191–1196. <https://doi.org/10.1002/jsfa.6396>.
- Durmic, Z., Black, J.L., Martin, G.B., Vercoe, P.E., 2022. Harnessing plant bioactivity for enteric methane mitigation in Australia. *Anim. Prod. Sci.* 62 (12), 1160–1172. <https://doi.org/10.1071/AN21004>.
- Duthie, C.A., Rooke, J.A., Hyslop, J.J., Waterhouse, A., 2015. Methane emissions from two breeds of beef cows offered diets containing barley straw with either grass silage or brewers' grains. *Animal* 9 (10), 1680–1687. <https://doi.org/10.1017/S1751731115001251>.
- Elgersma, A., Søgaard, K., Jensen, S.K., 2015. Interrelations between herbage yield, α -tocopherol, β -carotene, lutein, protein, and fiber in non-leguminous forbs, forage legumes, and a grass-clover mixture as affected by harvest date. *J. Agric. Food Chem.* 63 (2), 406–414. <https://doi.org/10.1021/jf503658n>.
- Enriquez-Hidalgo, D., Gilliland, T., Deighton, M.H., O'Donovan, M., Hennessy, D., 2014. Milk production and enteric methane emissions by dairy cows grazing fertilized perennial ryegrass pasture with or without inclusion of white clover. *J. Dairy Sci.* 97 (3), 1400–1412. <https://doi.org/10.3168/jds.2013-7034>.
- Eugène, M., Klumpp, K., Sauvant, D., 2021. Methane mitigating options with forages fed to ruminants. *Grass Forage Sci.* 76 (2), 196–204. <https://doi.org/10.1111/gfs.12540>.
- European Commission. (2018). Regulation (EU) 2018/848 on organic production and labelling of organic product. Official Journal of the European Union, 2018 (L151), 1–92. (<https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/PDF/?uri=CELEX:32018R0848&from=EN>), accessed: May 1st, 2023.
- Ferris, C.P., Jiao, H.P., Murray, S., Gordon, A., Laidlaw, S., 2020. Effect of dairy cow genotype and concentrate feed level on cow performance and enteric methane emissions during grazing. *Agric. Food Sci.* 29 (2), 130–138. <https://doi.org/10.23986/afsci.83442>.

- Florentini, G., Carvalho, I.P.C., Messina, J.D., Castagnino, P.S., Berndt, A., Canesin, R.C., Frighetto, R.T.S., Berchielli, T.T., 2014. Effect of lipid sources with different fatty acid profiles on the intake, performance, and methane emissions of feedlot Nellore steers. *J. Anim. Sci.* 92 (4), 1613–1620. <https://doi.org/10.2527/jas.2013-6868>.
- Focant, M., Froidmont, E., Archambeau, Q., Dang Van, Q.C., Larondelle, Y., 2019. The effect of oak tannin (*Quercus robur*) and hops (*Humulus lupulus*) on dietary nitrogen efficiency, methane emission, and milk fatty acid composition of dairy cows fed a low-protein diet including linseed. *J. Dairy Sci.* 102 (2), 1144–1159. <https://doi.org/10.3168/jds.2018-15479>.
- Fraser, M.D., Fleming, H.R., Moorby, J.M., 2014. Traditional vs modern: Role of breed type in determining enteric methane emissions from cattle grazing as part of contrasting grassland-based systems. *PLoS ONE* 9 (9). <https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pone.0107861>.
- Furrer, C., Grüter, L., 2020. Industrie-Nebenprodukte für Futtermittel. *UFA Rev.* (<https://www.ufarevue.ch/nutztiere/industrie-nebenprodukte-fuer-futtermittel>) accessed: May 1st, 2023.
- Garnsworthy, P.C., Marsden, M., Goodman, J.R., Saunders, N., 2021. Inclusion of wheat dried distillers' grains with solubles from bioethanol plants in diets for dairy cows. *Animals* 11 (1), 1–18. <https://doi.org/10.3390/ani11010070>.
- Gere, J.I., Bualó, R.A., Perini, A.L., Arias, R.D., Ortega, F.M., Wulff, A.E., Berra, G., 2021. Methane emission factors for beef cows in Argentina: effect of diet quality. *N. Z. J. Agric. Res.* 64 (2), 260–268. <https://doi.org/10.1080/00288233.2019.1621355>.
- Gidlund, H., Hetta, M., Krizsan, S.J., Lemosquet, S., Huhtanen, P., 2015. Effects of soybean meal or canola meal on milk production and methane emissions in lactating dairy cows fed grass silage-based diets. *J. Dairy Sci.* 98 (11), 8093–8106. <https://doi.org/10.3168/jds.2015-9757>.
- Gidlund, H., Hetta, M., Huhtanen, P., 2017. Milk production and methane emissions from dairy cows fed a low or high proportion of red clover silage and an incremental level of rapeseed expeller. *Livest. Sci.* 197 (January), 73–81. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.livsci.2017.01.009>.
- Goopy, J.P., Goopy, J.P., Korir, D., Korir, D., Pelster, D., Ali, A.I.M., Wassie, S.E., Schlecht, E., Dickhoefer, U., Merbold, L., Butterbach-Bahl, K., Butterbach-Bahl, K., 2020. Severe below-maintenance feed intake increases methane yield from enteric fermentation in cattle. *Br. J. Nutr.* 123 (11), 1239–1246. <https://doi.org/10.1017/S0007114519003350>.
- Grace, C., Boland, T.M., Sheridan, H., Brennan, E., Fritch, R., Lynch, M.B., 2019. The effect of grazing versus cutting on dry matter production of multispecies and perennial ryegrass-only swards. *Grass Forage Sci.* 74 (3), 437–449. <https://doi.org/10.1111/gfs.12440>.
- Gregorini, P., Villalba, J.J., Chilbroste, P., Provenza, F.D., 2017. Grazing management: setting the table, designing the menu and influencing the diner. *Anim. Prod. Sci.* 57 (7), 1248–1268. <https://doi.org/10.1071/AN16637>.
- Hammond, K.J., Burke, J.L., Koolaard, J.P., Muetzel, S., Pinares-Patiño, C.S., Waghorn, G.C., 2013. Effects of feed intake on enteric methane emissions from sheep fed fresh white clover (*Trifolium repens*) and perennial ryegrass (*Lolium perenne*) forages. *Anim. Feed Sci. Technol.* 179 (1–4), 121–132. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.anifeeds.2012.11.004>.
- Hammond, K.J., Pacheco, D., Burke, J.L., Koolaard, J.P., Muetzel, S., Waghorn, G.C., 2014. The effects of fresh forages and feed intake level on digesta kinetics and enteric methane emissions from sheep. *Anim. Feed Sci. Technol.* 193, 32–43. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.anifeeds.2014.04.005>.
- Hammond, K.J., Humphries, D.J., Westbury, D.B., Thompson, A., Crompton, L.A., Kirton, P., Green, C., Reynolds, C.K., 2014. The inclusion of forage mixtures in the diet of growing dairy heifers: Impacts on digestion, energy utilisation, and methane emissions. *Agric., Ecosyst. Environ.* 197, 88–95. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.agee.2014.07.016>.
- Hammond, K.J., Humphries, D.J., Crompton, L.A., Kirton, P., Reynolds, C.K., 2015. Effects of forage source and extruded linseed supplementation on methane emissions from growing dairy cattle of differing body weights. *J. Dairy Sci.* 98 (11), 8066–8077. <https://doi.org/10.3168/jds.2015-9669>.
- Hart, K.J., Martin, P.G., Foley, P.A., Kenny, D.A., Boland, T.M., 2009. Effect of sward dry matter digestibility on methane production, ruminal fermentation, and microbial populations of zero-grazed beef cattle. *J. Anim. Sci.* 87 (10), 3342–3350. <https://doi.org/10.2527/jas.2009-1786>.
- Hart, K.J., Huntington, J.A., Wilkinson, R.G., Bartram, C.G., Sinclair, L.A., 2014. The influence of grass silage-to-maize silage ratio and concentrate composition on methane emissions, performance and milk composition of dairy cows. *Animal* 9 (6), 983–991. <https://doi.org/10.1017/S1751731115000208>.
- Hart, K.J., Jones, H.G., Waddams, K.E., Worgan, H.J., Zweifel, B., Newbold, C.J., 2019. An Essential Oil Blend Decreases Methane Emissions and Increases Milk Yield in Dairy Cows. *Open J. Anim. Sci.* 09 (03), 259–267. <https://doi.org/10.4236/ojas.2019.93022>.
- Hassanat, F., Benchaar, C., 2021. Corn silage-based diet supplemented with increasing amounts of linseed oil: Effects on methane production, rumen fermentation, nutrient digestibility, nitrogen utilization, and milk production of dairy cows. *J. Dairy Sci.* 104 (5), 5375–5390. <https://doi.org/10.3168/jds.2020-18853>.
- Hassanat, F., Gervais, R., Julien, C., Massé, D.I., Lettat, A., Chouinard, P.Y., Petit, H.V., Benchaar, C., 2013. Replacing alfalfa silage with corn silage in dairy cow diets: effects on enteric methane production, ruminal fermentation, digestion, N balance, and milk production. *J. Dairy Sci.* 96 (7), 4553–4567. <https://doi.org/10.3168/jds.2012-6480>.
- Hassanat, F., Gervais, R., Massé, D.I., Petit, H.V., Benchaar, C., 2014. Methane production, nutrient digestion, ruminal fermentation, N balance, and milk production of cows fed timothy silage- or alfalfa silage-based diets. *J. Dairy Sci.* 97 (10), 6463–6474. <https://doi.org/10.3168/jds.2014-8069>.
- Hassanat, F., Gervais, R., Benchaar, C., 2017. Methane production, ruminal fermentation characteristics, nutrient digestibility, nitrogen excretion, and milk production of dairy cows fed conventional or brown midrib corn silage. *J. Dairy Sci.* 100 (4), 2625–2636. <https://doi.org/10.3168/jds.2016-11862>.
- Hatew, B., Podesta, S.C., Van Laar, H., Pellikaan, W.F., Ellis, J.L., Dijkstra, J., Bannink, A., 2015. Effects of dietary starch content and rate of fermentation on methane production in lactating dairy cows. *J. Dairy Sci.* 98 (1), 486–499. <https://doi.org/10.3168/jds.2014-8427>.
- Hatew, B., Bannink, A., van Laar, H., de Jonge, L.H., Dijkstra, J., 2016. Increasing harvest maturity of whole-plant corn silage reduces methane emission of lactating dairy cows. *J. Dairy Sci.* 99 (1), 354–368. <https://doi.org/10.3168/jds.2015-10047>.
- Hellwing, A.L.F., Sørensen, M.T., Weisbjerg, M.R., Vestergaard, M., Lund, P., 2012. Can rapeseed lower methane emission from heifers? *Acta Agric. Scand. A: Anim. Sci.* 62 (4), 259–262. <https://doi.org/10.1080/09064702.2013.788203>.
- Hindrichsen, I.K., Wettstein, H.R., Machmüller, A., Kreuzer, M., 2006. Methane emission, nutrient degradation and nitrogen turnover in dairy cows and their slurry at different milk production scenarios with and without concentrate supplementation. *Agric., Ecosyst. Environ.* 113 (1–4), 150–161. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.agee.2005.09.004>.
- Hironaka, R., Mathison, G.W., Kerrigan, B.K., Vlach, I., 1996. The effect of pelleting of alfalfa hay on methane production and digestibility by steers. *Sci. Total Environ.* 180 (3), 221–227. [https://doi.org/10.1016/0048-9697\(95\)04948-7](https://doi.org/10.1016/0048-9697(95)04948-7).
- Hoffmann, A., Cardoso, A.S., Fonseca, N.V.B., Romanzini, E.P., Siniscalchi, D., Berndt, A., Ruggieri, A.C., Reis, R.A., 2021. Effects of supplementation with corn distillers' dried grains on animal performance, nitrogen balance, and enteric CH₄ emissions of young Nellore bulls fed a high-tropical forage diet. *Animal* 15 (3), 100155. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.animal.2020.100155>.
- Hofstetter, P., Frey, H.J., Gazzarin, C., Wyss, U., Kunz, P., 2014. Dairy farming: Indoor v. pasture-based feeding. *J. Agric. Sci.* 152 (6), 994–1011. <https://doi.org/10.1017/S0021859614000227>.
- Hristov, A.N., Lee, C., Cassidy, T., Heyler, K., Tekippe, J.A., Varga, G.A., Corl, B., Brandt, R.C., 2013. Effect of *Origanum vulgare* L. leaves on rumen fermentation, production, and milk fatty acid composition in lactating dairy cows. *J. Dairy Sci.* 96 (2), 1189–1202. <https://doi.org/10.3168/jds.2012-5975>.
- Huber, R., Le'Clec'h, S., Buchmann, N., Finger, R., 2022. Economic value of three grassland ecosystem services when managed at the regional and farm scale. *Sci. Rep.* 12 (1), 1–13. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41598-022-08198-w>.
- Hunt, S.R., MacAdam, J.W., Reeve, J.R., 2015. Establishment of birdsfoot trefoil (*Lotus corniculatus*) pastures on organic dairy farms in the Mountain West USA. *Org. Agric.* 5 (1), 63–77. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s13165-014-0091-1>.
- Huyen, N.T., Desrués, O., Alferink, S.J.J., Zandstra, T., Verstegen, M.W.A., Hendriks, W.H., Pellikaan, W.F., 2016. Inclusion of sainfoin (*Onobrychis viciifolia*) silage in dairy cow rations affects nutrient digestibility, nitrogen utilization, energy balance, and methane emissions. *J. Dairy Sci.* 99 (5), 3566–3577. <https://doi.org/10.3168/jds.2015-10583>.
- Isbell, F., Craven, D., Connolly, J., Loreau, M., Schmid, B., Beierkuhnlein, C., Bezemer, T.M., Bonin, C., Bruehlheide, H., De Luca, E., 2015. Biodiversity increases the resistance of ecosystem productivity to climate extremes. *Nature* 526 (7574), 574–577. <https://doi.org/10.1038/nature15374>.
- Jayanegara, A., Leiber, F., Kreuzer, M., 2012. Meta-analysis of the relationship between dietary tannin level and methane formation in ruminants from in vivo and in vitro experiments. *J. Anim. Physiol. Anim. Nutr.* 96 (3), 365–375. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1439-0396.2011.01172.x>.

- Jiao, H.P., Dale, A.J., Carson, A.F., Murray, S., Gordon, A.W., Ferris, C.P., 2014. Effect of concentrate feed level on methane emissions from grazing dairy cows. *J. Dairy Sci.* 97 (11), 7043–7053. <https://doi.org/10.3168/jds.2014-7979>.
- Jonker, A., Molano, G., Sandoval, E., Taylor, P.S., Antwi, C., C. G. P., 2014. BRIEF COMMUNICATION: methane emissions by sheep offered high sugar or conventional perennial ryegrass at two allowances. *Proc. N. Z. Soc. Anim. Prod.* 74 (September), 145–147. <https://doi.org/10.13140/2.1.4565.6326>.
- Jonker, A., Molano, G., Antwi, C., Waghorn, G.C., 2016. Enteric methane and carbon dioxide emissions measured using respiration chambers, the sulfur hexafluoride tracer technique, and a greenfeed head-chamber system from beef heifers fed alfalfa silage at three allowances and four feeding frequencies. *J. Anim. Sci.* 94 (10), 4326–4337. <https://doi.org/10.2527/jas.2016-0646>.
- Jonker, A., Molano, G., Sandoval, E., Taylor, P.S., Antwi, C., Olinga, S., Cosgrove, G.P., 2018. Methane emissions differ between sheep offered a conventional diploid, a high-sugar diploid or a tetraploid perennial ryegrass cultivar at two allowances at three times of the year. *Anim. Prod. Sci.* 58 (6), 1043–1048. <https://doi.org/10.1071/AN15597>.
- Jonker, A., Farrell, L., Scobie, D., Dynes, R., Edwards, G., Hague, H., McAuliffe, R., Taylor, A., Knight, T., Waghorn, G., 2019. Methane and carbon dioxide emissions from lactating dairy cows grazing mature ryegrass/white clover or a diverse pasture comprising ryegrass, legumes and herbs. *Anim. Prod. Sci.* 59 (6), 1063–1069. <https://doi.org/10.1071/AN18019>.
- Judy, J.V., Bachman, G.C., Brown-Brandl, T.M., Fernando, S.C., Hales, K.E., Miller, P.S., Stowell, R.R., Kononoff, P.J., 2019. Reducing methane production with corn oil and calcium sulfate: responses on whole-animal energy and nitrogen balance in dairy cattle. *J. Dairy Sci.* 102 (3), 2054–2067. <https://doi.org/10.3168/jds.2018-14567>.
- Kasuya, H., Takahashi, J., 2010. Methane emissions from dry cows fed grass or legume silage. *Asian-Australas. J. Anim. Sci.* 23 (5), 563–566. <https://doi.org/10.5713/ajas.2010.90488>.
- Keogh, B., Mcgrath, T., Grant, J., 2012. The effect of sowing date and nitrogen on the dry-matter yield and nitrogen content of forage rape (*Brassica napus* L.) and stubble turnips (*Brassica rapa* L.) in Ireland. *Grass Forage Sci.* 67 (1), 2–12. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1365-2494.2011.00815.x>.
- Khiaosa-Ard, R., Zebeli, Q., 2013. Meta-analysis of the effects of essential oils and their bioactive compounds on rumen fermentation characteristics and feed efficiency in ruminants. *J. Anim. Sci.* 91 (4), 1819–1830. <https://doi.org/10.2527/jas.2012-5691>.
- Kidane, A., Prestlokken, E., Zoralis, K., Steinshamn, H., 2018. Effects of three short-term pasture allocation methods on milk production, methane emission and grazing behaviour by dairy cows. *Acta Agric. Scand. A: Anim. Sci.* 68 (2), 87–102. <https://doi.org/10.1080/09064702.2019.1577912>.
- Kim, J.Y., Ghassemi Nejad, J., Park, J.Y., Lee, B.H., Hanada, M., Kim, B.W., Sung, K.I., 2018. In vivo evaluation of garlic (*Allium sativum*) supplementation to rice straw-based diet on mitigation of CH₄ and CO₂ emissions and blood profiles using crossbreed rams. *J. Sci. Food Agric.* 98 (14), 5197–5204. <https://doi.org/10.1002/jsfa.9055>.
- Knapp, J.R., Laur, G.L., Vadas, P.A., Weiss, W.P., Tricarico, J.M., 2014. Invited review: Enteric methane in dairy cattle production: Quantifying the opportunities and impact of reducing emissions. *J. Dairy Sci.* 97 (6), 3231–3261. <https://doi.org/10.3168/jds.2013-7234>.
- Kolling, G.J., Stivanin, S.C.B., Gabbi, A.M., Machado, F.S., Ferreira, A.L., Campos, M.M., Tomich, T.R., Cunha, C.S., Dill, S.W., Pereira, L.G.R., Fischer, V., 2018. Performance and methane emissions in dairy cows fed oregano and green tea extracts as feed additives. *J. Dairy Sci.* 101 (5), 4221–4234. <https://doi.org/10.3168/jds.2017-13841>.
- Lagrange, S., Beauchemin, K.A., MacAdam, J., Villalba, J.J., 2020. Grazing diverse combinations of tanniferous and non-tanniferous legumes: implications for beef cattle performance and environmental impact. *Sci. Total Environ.* 746, 140788. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.scitotenv.2020.140788>.
- Lee, J.M., Woodward, S.L., Waghorn, G.C., Clark, D.A., 2004. Methane emissions by dairy cows fed increasing proportions of white clover (*Trifolium repens*) in pasture. *Proc. N. Z. Grassl. Assoc.* 151–155. <https://doi.org/10.33584/jnzg.2004.66.2552>.
- Lee, J.M., Hemmingson, N.R., Minnee, E.M.K., Clark, C.E.F., 2015. Management strategies for chicory (*Cichorium intybus*) and plantain (*Plantago lanceolata*): Impact on dry matter yield, nutritive characteristics and plant density. *Crop Pasture Sci.* 66 (2), 168–183. <https://doi.org/10.1071/CP14181>.
- Leiber, F., 2022. Let them graze! Potentials of ruminant production outside the feed-food competition. In *Managing Healthy Livestock Production and Consumption*. Elsevier, pp. 137–148. <https://doi.org/10.1016/B978-0-12-823019-0.00009-X>.
- Leiber, F., Schenk, I.K., Maeschli, A., Ivemeyer, S., Zeitz, J.O., Moakes, S., Klocke, P., Staehli, P., Notz, C., Walkenhorst, M., 2017. Implications of feed concentrate reduction in organic grassland-based dairy systems: a long-term on-farm study. *Animal* 1–10. <https://doi.org/10.1017/S175173117000830>.
- Leiber, F., Walkenhorst, M., Holinger, M., 2020. The relevance of feed diversity and choice in nutrition of ruminant livestock. *Landbauforschung* 70 (1), 35–38. <https://doi.org/10.3220/LBF1592393539000>.
- Lejonklev, J., Kidmose, U., Jensen, S., Petersen, M.A., Helwing, A.L.F., Mortensen, G., Weisbjerg, M.R., Larsen, M.K., 2016. Short communication: Effect of oregano and caraway essential oils on the production and flavor of cow milk. *J. Dairy Sci.* 99 (10), 7898–7903. <https://doi.org/10.3168/jds.2016-10910>.
- Lettat, A., Hassanat, F., Benchaar, C., 2013. Corn silage in dairy cow diets to reduce ruminal methanogenesis: Effects on the rumen metabolically active microbial communities. *J. Dairy Sci.* 96 (8), 5237–5248. <https://doi.org/10.3168/jds.2012-6481>.
- LfL Institut für Pflanzenbau und Pflanzenzüchtung, 2016. Luzerne Anbau - Konservierung - Verfütterung. Bayerische Landesanstalt für Landwirtschaft (LfL).
- Li, G., Kemp, P.D., 2005. Forage chicory (*Cichorium intybus* L.): a review of its agronomy and animal production. *Adv. Agron.* 88 (05), 187–222. [https://doi.org/10.1016/S0065-2113\(05\)88005-8](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0065-2113(05)88005-8).
- Lima, P.R., Apdini, T., Freire, A.S., Santana, A.S., Moura, L.M.L., Nascimento, J.C.S., Rodrigues, R.T.S., Dijkstra, J., Garcez Neto, A.F., Queiroz, M.A.Á., Menezes, D.R., 2019. Dietary supplementation with tannin and soybean oil on intake, digestibility, feeding behavior, ruminal protozoa and methane emission in sheep. *Anim. Feed Sci. Technol.* 249 (December 2017), 10–17. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.anifeedsci.2019.01.017>.
- Lind, L., Sizmaz, Ö., Weldon, S., Dragan Miladinovic, D., Jørgensen, G.M., 2020. Enteric methane emissions from sheep fed diets including biochar. *Meet. Future Demands Grassl. Prod.* 306.
- Lind, V., Weisbjerg, M.R., Jørgensen, G.M., Fernandez-yepes, J.E., Arbes, L., Molina-alcaide, E., 2020. Ruminal fermentation, growth rate and methane production in sheep fed diets including white clover, soybean meal or porphyra sp, 1–14 *Animal* 10 (1), 79. <https://doi.org/10.3390/ani10010079>.
- Liu, C., Zhu, Z.P., Shang, B., Chen, Y.X., Guo, T.J., Luo, Y.M., 2013. Long-term effects of ensiled cornstalk diet on methane emission, rumen fermentation, methanogenesis and weight gain in sheep. *Small Rumin. Res.* 115 (1–3), 15–20. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.smallrumres.2013.07.011>.
- Lovett, D.K., Stack, L.J., Lovell, S., Callan, J., Flynn, B., Hawkins, M., O'Mara, F.P., 2005. Manipulating enteric methane emissions and animal performance of late-lactation dairy cows through concentrate supplementation at pasture. *J. Dairy Sci.* 88 (8), 2836–2842. [https://doi.org/10.3168/jds.S0022-0302\(05\)72964-7](https://doi.org/10.3168/jds.S0022-0302(05)72964-7).
- Loza, C., Reinsch, T., Loges, R., Taube, F., Gere, J.I., Kluß, C., Hasler, M., Malisch, C.S., 2021. Methane emission and milk production from jersey cows grazing perennial ryegrass–white clover and multispecies forage mixtures. *Agric. (Switz.)* 11 (2), 1–17. <https://doi.org/10.3390/agriculture11020175>.
- Lüscher, A., Barkaoui, K., Finn, J.A., Suter, D., Suter, M., Voltaire, F., 2022. Using plant diversity to reduce vulnerability and increase drought resilience of permanent and sown productive grasslands. *Grass Forage Sci.* 77 (4), 235–246. <https://doi.org/10.1111/gfs.12578>.
- Ma, T., Chen, D., Tu, Y., Zhang, N., Si, B., Deng, K., Diao, Q., 2016. Effect of supplementation of allicin on methanogenesis and ruminal microbial flora in Dorper crossbred ewes. *J. Anim. Sci. Biotechnol.* 7 (1), 1–7. <https://doi.org/10.1186/s40104-015-0057-5>.
- Ma, T., Chen, D.D., Tu, Y., Zhang, N.F., Si, B.W., Diao, Q.Y., 2017. Dietary supplementation with mulberry leaf flavonoids inhibits methanogenesis in sheep. *Anim. Sci. J.* 88 (1), 72–78. <https://doi.org/10.1111/asj.12556>.
- MacAdam, J.W., & Griggs, T.C. (2013). Irrigated birdsfoot trefoil variety trial: Forage nutritive value. March, 1–6. (https://digitalcommons.usu.edu/extension_curall/1336/), accessed: May 1st, 2023.
- Machado, F.S., Rodríguez, N.M., Gonçalves, L.C., Rodrigues, J.A.S., Ribas, M.N., Póssas, F.P., Jayme, D.G., Pereira, L.G.R., Chaves, A.V., Tomich, T.R., 2015. Energy partitioning and methane emission by sheep fed sorghum silages at different maturation stages. *Arq. Bras. De. Med. Vet. e Zootec.* 67 (3), 790–800. <https://doi.org/10.1590/1678-4162-7177>.
- Machmüller, A., Ossowski, D.A., Kreuzer, M., 2000. Comparative evaluation of the effects of coconut oil, oilseeds and crystalline fat on methane release, digestion and energy balance in lambs. *Anim. Feed Sci. Technol.* 85 (1–2), 41–60. [https://doi.org/10.1016/S0377-8401\(00\)00126-7](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0377-8401(00)00126-7).
- Malisch, C.S., Suter, D., Studer, B., Lüscher, A., 2017. Multifunctional benefits of sainfoin mixtures: effects of partner species, sowing density and cutting regime. *Grass Forage Sci.* 72 (4), 794–805. <https://doi.org/10.1111/gfs.12278>.

- Mao, H.L., Wang, J.K., Zhou, Y.Y., Liu, J.X., 2010. Effects of addition of tea saponins and soybean oil on methane production, fermentation and microbial population in the rumen of growing lambs. *Livest. Sci.* 129 (1–3), 56–62. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.livsci.2009.12.011>.
- Martin, C., Rouel, J., Jouany, J.P., Doreau, M., Chilliard, Y., 2008. Methane output and diet digestibility in response to feeding dairy cows crude linseed, extruded linseed, or linseed oil. *J. Anim. Sci.* 86 (10), 2642–2650. <https://doi.org/10.2527/jas.2007-0774>.
- Martin, C., Ferlay, A., Mosoni, P., Rochette, Y., Chilliard, Y., Doreau, M., 2016. Increasing linseed supply in dairy cow diets based on hay or corn silage: Effect on enteric methane emission, rumen microbial fermentation, and digestion. *J. Dairy Sci.* 99 (5), 3445–3456. <https://doi.org/10.3168/jds.2015-10110>.
- Mata e Silva, B.C., Lopes, F.C.F., Pereira, L.G.R., Tomich, T.R., Morenz, M.J.F., Martins, C.E., Gomide, C.A.M., Paciullo, D.S.C., Maurício, R.M., Chaves, A.V., 2017. Effect of sunflower oil supplementation on methane emissions of dairy cows grazing *Urochloa brizantha* cv. marandu1. *Anim. Prod. Sci.* 57 (7), 1431–1436. <https://doi.org/10.1071/AN16470>.
- McCaughey, W.P., Wittenberg, K., Corrigan, D., 1997. Methane production by steers on pasture. *Can. J. Anim. Sci.* 77 (3), 519–524. <https://doi.org/10.4141/A96-137>.
- McCaughey, W.P., Wittenberg, K., Corrigan, D., 1999. Impact of pasture type on methane production by lactating beef cows. *Can. J. Anim. Sci.* 79 (2), 221–226. <https://doi.org/10.4141/A98-107>.
- McDonnell, R.P., Hart, K.J., Boland, T.M., Kelly, A.K., McGee, M., Kenny, D.A., 2016. Effect of divergence in phenotypic residual feed intake on methane emissions, ruminal fermentation, and apparent whole-tract digestibility of beef heifers across three contrasting diets. *J. Anim. Sci.* 94 (3), 1179–1193. <https://doi.org/10.2527/jas.2015-0080>.
- McGeough, E.J., O'Kiely, P., Hart, K.J., Moloney, A.P., Boland, T.M., Kenny, D.A., 2010. Methane emissions, feed intake, performance, digestibility, and rumen fermentation of finishing beef cattle offered whole-crop wheat silages differing in grain content. *J. Anim. Sci.* 88 (8), 2703–2716. <https://doi.org/10.2527/jas.2009-2750>.
- McGinn, S.M., Beauchemin, K.A., Coates, T., Colombatto, D., 2004. Methane emissions from beef cattle: effects of monensin, sunflower oil, enzymes, yeast, and fumaric acid. *J. Anim. Sci.* 82 (11), 3346–3356. <https://doi.org/10.2527/2004.82113346x>.
- McGinn, S.M., Chung, Y.-H., Beauchemin, K.A., Iwaasa, A.D., Grainger, C., 2009. Use of corn distillers' dried grains to reduce enteric methane loss from beef cattle. *Can. J. Anim. Sci.* 89 (3), 409–413. <https://doi.org/10.4141/cjas08133>.
- Meale, S.J., Chaves, A.V., Mcallister, T.A., Iwaasa, A.D., Yang, W.Z., Benchaar, C., 2014. Including essential oils in lactating dairy cow diets: effects on methane emissions. *Anim. Prod. Sci.* 54 (9), 1215–1218. <https://doi.org/10.1071/AN14152>.
- Min, B.R., Solaiman, S., Waldrip, H.M., Parker, D., Todd, R.W., Brauer, D., 2020. Dietary mitigation of enteric methane emissions from ruminants: a review of plant tannin mitigation options. *Anim. Nutr.* 6 (3), 231–246. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.aninu.2020.05.002>.
- Minnee, E.M.K., Bluet, S.J., Woodward, S.L., Laboyrie, P.G., 2007. Management of *Lotus corniculatus* under dairy cow grazing. *Proc. N. Z. Grassl. Assoc.* 47–51. <https://doi.org/10.33584/jnzg.2007.69.2685>.
- Mirzaie, A., Mohammadi, K., Parvini, S., Khoramivafa, M., Saeidi, M., 2020. Yield quantity and quality of two linseed (*Linum usitatissimum* L.) cultivars as affected by sowing date. *Ind. Crops Prod.* 158 (October), 112947. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.indcrop.2020.112947>.
- Moate, P.J., Williams, S.R.O., Grainger, C., Hannah, M.C., Ponnampalam, E.N., Eckard, R.J., 2011. Influence of cold-pressed canola, brewers grains and hominy meal as dietary supplements suitable for reducing enteric methane emissions from lactating dairy cows. *Anim. Feed Sci. Technol.* 166–167, 254–264. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.anifeeds.2011.04.069>.
- Moate, P.J., Williams, S.R.O., Torok, V.A., Hannah, M.C., Ribaux, B.E., Tavendale, M.H., Eckard, R.J., Jacobs, J.L., Auld, M.J., Wales, W.J., 2014. Grape marc reduces methane emissions when fed to dairy cows. *J. Dairy Sci.* 97 (8), 5073–5087. <https://doi.org/10.3168/jds.2013-7588>.
- Moate, P.J., Jacobs, J.L., Hixson, J.L., Deighton, M.H., Hannah, M.C., Morris, G.L., Ribaux, B.E., Wales, W.J., Williams, S.R.O., 2020. Effects of feeding either red or white grape marc on milk production and methane emissions from early-lactation dairy cows. *Animals* 10 (6). <https://doi.org/10.3390/ani10060976>.
- Mohammed, N., Ajisaka, N., Lila, Z.A., Hara, K., Mikuni, K., Hara, K., Kanda, S., Itabashi, H., 2004. Effect of Japanese horseradish oil on methane production and ruminal fermentation in vitro and in steers. *J. Anim. Sci.* 82 (6), 1839–1846. <https://doi.org/10.2527/2004.8261839x>.
- Molano, G., Clark, H., 2008. The effect of level of intake and forage quality on methane production by sheep. *Aust. J. Exp. Agric.* 48 (1–2), 219–222. <https://doi.org/10.1071/EA07253>.
- Moloney, T., Sheridan, H., Grant, J., O'Riordan, E.G., O'Kiely, P., 2020. Yield of binary- and multi-species swards relative to single-species swards in intensive silage systems. *Ir. J. Agric. Food Res.* 59 (1), 12–26. <https://doi.org/10.2478/ijaf-2020-0002>.
- Moss, A.R., Givens, D.I., 2002. The effect of supplementing grass silage with soya bean meal on digestibility, in sacco degradability, rumen fermentation and methane production in sheep. *Anim. Feed Sci. Technol.* 97 (3–4), 127–143. [https://doi.org/10.1016/S0377-8401\(02\)00022-6](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0377-8401(02)00022-6).
- Muñoz, C., Hube, S., Morales, J.M., Yan, T., Ungerfeld, E.M., 2015. Effects of concentrate supplementation on enteric methane emissions and milk production of grazing dairy cows. *Livest. Sci.* 175, 37–46. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.livsci.2015.02.001>.
- Muñoz, C., Letelier, P.A., Ungerfeld, E.M., Morales, J.M., Hube, S., Pérez-Prieto, L.A., 2016. Effects of pregrazing herbage mass in late spring on enteric methane emissions, dry matter intake, and milk production of dairy cows. *J. Dairy Sci.* 99 (10), 7945–7955. <https://doi.org/10.3168/jds.2016-10919>.
- Muñoz, C., Herrera, D., Hube, S., Morales, J., Ungerfeld, E.M., 2018. Effects of dietary concentrate supplementation on enteric methane emissions and performance of late lactation dairy cows. *Chil. J. Agric. Res.* 78 (3), 429–437. <https://doi.org/10.4067/S0718-58392018000300429>.
- Na, R., Dong, H., Zhu, Z., Chen, Y., Xin, H., 2013. Effects of forage type and dietary concentrate to forage ratio on methane emissions and rumen fermentation characteristics of dairy cows in China. *Trans. ASABE* 56 (3), 1115–1122. <https://doi.org/10.13031/trans.56.9972>.
- Neto, A.J., Messina, J.D., Ribeiro, A.F., Vito, E.S., Rossi, L.G., Berchielli, T.T., 2015. Effect of starch-based supplementation level combined with oil on intake, performance, and methane emissions of growing Nellore bulls on pasture. *J. Anim. Sci.* 93 (5), 2275–2284. <https://doi.org/10.2527/jas.2014-8500>.
- Niderkorn, V., Martin, C., Rochette, Y., Julien, S., Baumont, R., 2015. Associative effects between orchardgrass and red clover silages on voluntary intake and digestion in sheep: Evidence of a synergy on digestible dry matter intake. *J. Anim. Sci.* 93 (10), 4967–4976. <https://doi.org/10.2527/jas.2015-9178>.
- Niderkorn, V., Martin, C., Le Morvan, A., Rochette, Y., Awad, M., Baumont, R., 2017. Associative effects between fresh perennial ryegrass and white clover on dynamics of intake and digestion in sheep. *Grass Forage Sci.* 72 (4), 691–699. <https://doi.org/10.1111/gfs.12270>.
- Niderkorn, V., Copani, G., Martin, C., Maxin, G., Torrent, A., Anglard, F., Rochette, Y., Ginane, C., 2019. Effects of including bioactive legumes in grass silage on digestion parameters, nitrogen balance and methane emissions in sheep. *Grass Forage Sci.* 74 (4), 626–635. <https://doi.org/10.1111/gfs.12454>.
- Niderkorn, V., Martin, C., Bernard, M., Le Morvan, A., Rochette, Y., Baumont, R., 2019. Effect of increasing the proportion of chicory in forage-based diets on intake and digestion by sheep. *Animal* 13 (4), 718–726. <https://doi.org/10.1017/S1757173118002185>.
- Nishida, T., Eruden, B., Hosoda, K., Matsuyama, H., Xu, C., Shiyo, S., 2007. Digestibility, methane production and chewing activity of steers fed whole-crop round bale corn silage preserved at three maturities. *Anim. Feed Sci. Technol.* 135 (1–2), 42–51. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.anifeeds.2006.05.018>.
- Niu, M., Kebreab, E., Hristov, A.N., Oh, J., Arndt, C., Bannink, A., Bayat, A.R., Brito, A.F., Boland, T., Casper, D., Crompton, L.A., Dijkstra, J., Eugène, M.A., Garnsworthy, P.C., Haque, M.N., Helling, A.L.F., Huhtanen, P., Kreuzer, M., Kuhl, B., Yu, Z., 2018. Prediction of enteric methane production, yield, and intensity in dairy cattle using an intercontinental database. *Glob. Change Biol.* 24 (8), 3368–3389. <https://doi.org/10.1111/gcb.14094>.
- O'Neill, B.F., Deighton, M.H., O'Loughlin, B.M., Galvin, N., O'Donovan, M., Lewis, E., 2012. The effects of supplementing grazing dairy cows with partial mixed ration on enteric methane emissions and milk production during mid to late lactation. *J. Dairy Sci.* 95 (11), 6582–6590. <https://doi.org/10.3168/jds.2011-5257>.
- Olijhoek, D.W., Helling, A.L.F., Grevsen, K., Haveman, L.S., Chowdhury, M.R., Lövendahl, P., Weisbjerg, M.R., Noel, S.J., Højberg, O., Wiking, L., Lund, P., 2019. Effect of dried oregano (*Origanum vulgare* L.) plant material in feed on methane production, rumen fermentation, nutrient digestibility, and milk fatty acid composition in dairy cows. *J. Dairy Sci.* 102 (11), 9902–9918. <https://doi.org/10.3168/jds.2019-16329>.
- de Oliveira, S.G., Berchielli, T.T., Pedreira, M. dos S., Primavesi, O., Frighetto, R., Lima, M.A., 2007. Effect of tannin levels in sorghum silage and concentrate supplementation on apparent digestibility and methane emission in beef cattle. *Anim. Feed Sci. Technol.* 135 (3–4), 236–248. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.anifeeds.2006.07.012>.
- Özpunar, H., Avci, M., Acar, A.A., Aksu, S., İnal, F.N., Ay, E., İnal, İ., Gündel, F.D., Aktaş, A., Hatipoğlu, R., 2019. Determination of yields of bird's-foot trefoil (*Lotus corniculatus* L.) genotypes under Mediterranean climatic conditions. *Anadolu* 29 (1), 15–24.

- Pang, D., Yan, T., Trevisi, E., Krizsan, S.J., 2018. Effect of grain- or by-product-based concentrate fed with early- or late-harvested first-cut grass silage on dairy cow performance. *J. Dairy Sci.* 101 (8), 7133–7145. <https://doi.org/10.3168/jds.2018-14449>.
- Panthee, A., Matsuno, A., Al-Mamun, M., Sano, H., 2017. Effect of feeding garlic leaves on rumen fermentation, methane emission, plasma glucose kinetics, and nitrogen utilization in sheep. *J. Anim. Sci. Technol.* 59 (1), 1–9. <https://doi.org/10.1186/s40781-017-0139-3>.
- Patel, M., Wredle, E., Börjesson, G., Danielsson, R., Iwaasa, A.D., Spörndly, E., Bertilsson, J., 2011. Enteric methane emissions from dairy cows fed different proportions of highly digestible grass silage. *Acta Agric. Scand. A: Anim. Sci.* 61 (3), 128–136. <https://doi.org/10.1080/09064702.2011.616216>.
- Pedreira, M., dos, S., de Oliveira, S.G., Primavesi, O., de Lima, M.A., Frighetto, R.T.S., Berchielli, T.T., 2013. Methane emissions and estimates of ruminal fermentation parameters in beef cattle fed different dietary concentrate levels. *Rev. Bras. De. Zootec.* 42 (8), 592–598. <https://doi.org/10.1590/S1516-35982013000800009>.
- Pérez-Barbería, F.J., Mayes, R.W., Giráldez, J., Sánchez-Pérez, D., 2020. Ericaceous species reduce methane emissions in sheep and red deer: Respiration chamber measurements and predictions at the scale of European heathlands. *Sci. Total Environ.* 714, 136738. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.scitotenv.2020.136738>.
- Pinares-Patiño, C.S., Ulyatt, M.J., Waghorn, G.C., Lassey, K.R., Barry, T.N., Holmes, C.W., Johnson, D.E., 2003. Methane emission by alpaca and sheep fed on lucerne hay or grazed on pastures of perennial ryegrass/white clover or birdsfoot trefoil. *J. Agric. Sci.* 140 (2), 215–226. <https://doi.org/10.1017/S002185960300306X>.
- Pinares-Patiño, C.S., Baumont, R., Martin, C., 2003. Methane emissions by Charolais cows grazing a monospecific pasture of timothy at four stages of maturity. *Can. J. Anim. Sci.* 83 (4), 769–777. <https://doi.org/10.4141/A03-034>.
- Pinares-Patiño, C.S., Franco, F.E., Molano, G., Kjestrup, H., Sandoval, E., MacLean, S., Battistotti, M., Koolgaard, J., Laubach, J., 2016. Feed intake and methane emissions from cattle grazing pasture sprayed with canola oil. *Livest. Sci.* 184, 7–12. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.livsci.2015.11.020>.
- Pineda, G.S.H., Beltrán, P.E.P., Benaouda, M., García, J.M.P., Nova, F.A., Molina, L., Ortega, O.A.C., 2018. *Pithecellobium dulce*, *Tagetes erecta* and *Cosmos bipinnatus* on reducing enteric methane emission by dairy cows. *Cienc. Rural* 48 (10). <https://doi.org/10.1590/0103-8478cr20170484>.
- Poteko, J., Schrade, S., Zeyer, K., Mohn, J., Zaehner, M., Zeitz, J.O., Kreuzer, M., Schwarm, A., 2020. Methane emissions and milk fatty acid profiles in dairy cows fed linseed, measured at the group level in a naturally ventilated housing and individually in respiration chambers. *Animals* 10 (6), 1–18. <https://doi.org/10.3390/ani10061091>.
- Ramírez-Restrepo, C.A., Waghorn, G.C., Gillespie, H., Clark, H., 2020. Partition of dietary energy by sheep fed fresh ryegrass (*Lolium perenne*) with a wide-ranging composition and quality. *Anim. Prod. Sci.* 60 (8), 1008–1017. <https://doi.org/10.1071/AN19285>.
- Rey, C., Carron, C., Bruttin, B., Cottagnaud, A., Slacanin, I., 2002. La variété d'origan "Carva.". *Rev. Suisse De. Vitic. Arboric. Hortic.* 34 (2). (https://www.agroscope.admin.ch/agroscope/de/home/themen/pflanzenbau/gewuerz-medizinalpflanzen/liste-plantes-aromatiques-medicinales/origanum_jcr_content/par/columncontrols/items/0/column/externalcontent.bitexternalcontent.exturl.pdf/aHR0cHM6Ly9pcmEuYWdyb). accessed: May 1st 2023.
- Sala, F., Radulov, I., Ökrös, A., Crista, F., & Berbecea, A. (2008). FERTILISATION SYSTEMS AND RAPE BIOMASS PRODUCTION. *Bulletin of University of Agricultural Sciences and Veterinary Medicine Cluj-Napoca. Agriculture*, 65(1), 235–238. eISSN 1843–5386.
- Santos, B., Mwenya, B., Sar, C., Takahashi, J., 2007. Methane production and energy partition in sheep fed timothy silage-or hay-based diets. *J. Ilmu Ternak Dan. Vet.* 12 (1), 27–33.
- Saviani, J.V., Neto, A.B., de David, D.B., Bremm, C., Schons, R.M.T., Genro, T.C.M., do Amaral, G.A., Gere, J., McManus, C.M., Bayer, C., de Faccio Carvalho, P.C., 2014. Grazing intensity and stocking methods on animal production and methane emission by grazing sheep: Implications for integrated crop-livestock system. *Agric. Ecosyst. Environ.* 190, 112–119. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.agee.2014.02.008>.
- Saviani, J.V., Schons, R.M.T., Marchi, D.E., Freitas, T.S. de, da Silva Neto, G.F., Mezzalana, J.C., Berndt, A., Bayer, C., Carvalho, P.C. de F., 2018. Rotatinoous stocking: A grazing management innovation that has high potential to mitigate methane emissions by sheep. *J. Clean. Prod.* 186, 602–608. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jclepro.2018.03.162>.
- Schader, C., Muller, A., El-Hage Scialabba, N., Hecht, J., Isensee, A., Erb, K.H., Smith, P., Makkar, H.P.S., Klocke, P., Leiber, F., Schwegler, P., Stolze, M., Niggli, U., 2015. Impacts of feeding less food-competing feedstuffs to livestock on global food system sustainability. *J. R. Soc. Interface* 12 (113). <https://doi.org/10.1098/rsif.2015.0891>.
- Schwarm, A., Schweigel-Röntgen, M., Kreuzer, M., Ortmann, S., Gill, F., Kuhla, B., Meyer, U., Lohölter, M., Derno, M., 2015. Methane emission, digestive characteristics and faecal archaeol in heifers fed diets based on silage from brown midrib maize as compared to conventional maize. *Arch. Anim. Nutr.* 69 (3), 159–176. <https://doi.org/10.1080/1745039X.2015.1043211>.
- Silvestre, T., Lima, M.A., Dos Santos, G.B., Pereira, L.G.R., Machado, F.S., Tomich, T.R., Campos, M.M., Jonker, A., Rodrigues, P.H.M., Brandao, V.L.N., Marcondes, M. I., 2021. Effects of feeding level and breed composition on intake, digestibility, and methane emissions of dairy heifers. *Animals* 11 (3), 1–11. <https://doi.org/10.3390/ani11030586>.
- Soliva, C.R., Zeleke, A.B., Clément, C., Hess, H.D., Fievez, V., Kreuzer, M., 2008. In vitro screening of various tropical foliage, seeds, fruits and medicinal plants for low methane and high ammonia generating potentials in the rumen. *Anim. Feed Sci. Technol.* 147 (1–3), 53–71. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.anifeedsci.2007.09.009>.
- Sotiropoulou, D.E., Karamanos, A.J., 2010. Field studies of nitrogen application on growth and yield of Greek oregano (*Origanum vulgare* ssp. *hirtum* (Link) Ietswaart). *Ind. Crops Prod.* 32 (3), 450–457. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.indcrop.2010.06.014>.
- de Souza Filho, W., Nunes, P.A., de, A., Barro, R.S., Kunrath, T.R., de Almeida, G.M., Genro, T.C.M., Bayer, C., de Faccio Carvalho, P.C., 2019. Mitigation of enteric methane emissions through pasture management in integrated crop-livestock systems: Trade-offs between animal performance and environmental impacts. *J. Clean. Prod.* 213, 968–975. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jclepro.2018.12.245>.
- Spinei, M., Oroian, M., 2021. The potential of grape pomace varieties as a dietary source of pectic substances. *Foods* 10 (4). <https://doi.org/10.3390/foods10040867>.
- Staerfl, S.M., Zeitz, J.O., Kreuzer, M., Soliva, C.R., 2012. Methane conversion rate of bulls fattened on grass or maize silage as compared with the IPCC default values, and the long-term methane mitigation efficiency of adding acacia tannin, garlic, maca and lupine. *Agric. Ecosyst. Environ.* 148, 111–120. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.agee.2011.11.003>.
- Stefenoni, H.A., Räisänen, S.E., Cueva, S.F., Wasson, D.E., Lage, C.F.A., Melgar, A., Fetter, M.E., Smith, P., Hennessy, M., Vecchiarelli, B., Bender, J., Pitta, D., Cantrell, C.L., Yarish, C., Hristov, A.N., 2021. Effects of the macroalga *Asparagopsis taxiformis* and oregano leaves on methane emission, rumen fermentation, and lactational performance of dairy cows. *J. Dairy Sci.* 104 (4), 4157–4173. <https://doi.org/10.3168/jds.2020-19686>.
- Steinwider, A., Frickh, J., Luger, K., Guggenberger, T., Schauer, A., Huber, J., & Gruber, L. (2007). *Einfluss von Rationsgestaltung, Geschlecht und Mastendmasse auf Futtermittelaufnahme und Mastleistung bei Fleckvieh-Tieren*. Bundesanstalt für alpenländische Landwirtschaft Gumpenstein, Irnding, Austria.
- Stewart, E.K., Beauchemin, K.A., Dai, X., MacAdam, J.W., Christensen, R.G., Villalba, J.J., 2019. Effect of tannin-containing hays on enteric methane emissions and nitrogen partitioning in beef cattle. *J. Anim. Sci.* 97 (8), 3286–3299. <https://doi.org/10.1093/jas/skz206>.
- Sun, X., Henderson, G., Cox, F., Molano, G., Harrison, S.J., Luo, D., Janssen, P.H., Pacheco, D., 2015. Lambs fed fresh winter forage rape (*Brassica napus* L.) emit less methane than those fed perennial ryegrass (*Lolium perenne* L.), and possible mechanisms behind the difference. *PLoS ONE* 10 (3), 1–16. <https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pone.0119697>.
- Sun, X.Z., Hoskin, S.O., Muetzel, S., Molano, G., Clark, H., 2011. Effects of forage chicory (*Cichorium intybus*) and perennial ryegrass (*Lolium perenne*) on methane emissions in vitro and from sheep. *Anim. Feed Sci. Technol.* 166–167, 391–397. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.anifeedsci.2011.04.027>.
- Sun, X.Z., Hoskin, S.O., Zhang, G.G., Molano, G., Muetzel, S., Pinares-Patiño, C.S., Clark, H., Pacheco, D., 2012. Sheep fed forage chicory (*Cichorium intybus*) or perennial ryegrass (*Lolium perenne*) have similar methane emissions. *Anim. Feed Sci. Technol.* 172 (3–4), 217–225. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.anifeedsci.2011.11.007>.
- Sun, X.Z., Waghorn, G.C., Hoskin, S.O., Harrison, S.J., Muetzel, S., Pacheco, D., 2012. Methane emissions from sheep fed fresh brassicas (*Brassica* spp.) compared to perennial ryegrass (*Lolium perenne*). *Anim. Feed Sci. Technol.* 176 (1–4), 107–116. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.anifeedsci.2012.07.013>.
- Sun, X.Z., Maclean, S., Luo, D.W., Pacheco, D., 2014. Sheep fed five different summer forage brassicas emitted less methane than sheep fed perennial ryegrass/white clover pasture. *Proc. Aust. Soc. Anim. Prod.* 30, 98.
- Suter, D., & Frick, R. (2022). Luzerne "Königin der Futterpflanzen". *AGFF-Merkblätter: Ratgeber Für Den ÖLN- Und Bio-Futterbau*.
- Swiss granum. (2022). Durchschnittliche Erträge. Swiss Granum, Schweizerische Branchenorganisation Getreide, Ölsaaten und Eiweisspflanzen. (https://www.swissgranum.ch/documents/741931/8752445/2022-11-01_durchschnittliche_Ertraege.pdf/e027ff71-1075-cf15-5ff2-0d2ffdf11bb8), accessed: May 1st 2023.

- Taylor, J., Tisseyre, B., Bramley, R., Reid, A., 2005. A comparison of the spatial variability of vineyard yield in European and Australian production systems. *Precis. Agric.* 2005, *ECPA 2005* 907–914.
- Tekippe, J.A., Hristov, A.N., Heyley, K.S., Cassidy, T.W., Zheljzakov, V.D., Ferreira, J.F.S., Karnati, S.K., Varga, G.A., 2011. Rumen fermentation and production effects of *Origanum vulgare* L. leaves in lactating dairy cows. *J. Dairy Sci.* 94 (10), 5065–5079. <https://doi.org/10.3168/jds.2010-4095>.
- Terranova, M., Eggerschwiler, L., Ortmann, S., Clauss, M., Kreuzer, M., Schwarm, A., 2021. Increasing the proportion of hazel leaves in the diet of dairy cows reduced methane yield and excretion of nitrogen in volatile form, but not milk yield. *Anim. Feed Sci. Technol.* 276 (December 2020), 114790 <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.anifeeds.2020.114790>.
- Terry, S.A., Ribeiro, G.O., Gruninger, R.J., Chaves, A.V., Beauchemin, K.A., Okine, E., McAllister, T.A., 2019. A pine enhanced biochar does not decrease enteric CH₄ emissions, but alters the rumen microbiota. *Front. Vet. Sci.* 6 (September), 1–12. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fvets.2019.00308>.
- Tomkins, N.W., Denman, S.E., Pilajun, R., Wanapat, M., McSweeney, C.S., Elliott, R., 2015. Manipulating rumen fermentation and methanogenesis using an essential oil and monensin in beef cattle fed a tropical grass hay. *Anim. Feed Sci. Technol.* 200 (1), 25–34. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.anifeeds.2014.11.013>.
- Uddin, M.E., Santana, O.I., Weigel, K.A., Wattiaux, M.A., 2020. Enteric methane, lactation performances, digestibility, and metabolism of nitrogen and energy of Holsteins and Jerseys fed 2 levels of forage fiber from alfalfa silage or corn silage. *J. Dairy Sci.* 103 (7), 6087–6099. <https://doi.org/10.3168/jds.2019-17599>.
- Ugbogu, E.A., Elghandour, M.M.M.Y., Ikpeazu, V.O., Buendía, G.R., Molina, O.M., Arunsi, U.O., Emmanuel, O., Salem, A.Z.M., 2019. The potential impacts of dietary plant natural products on the sustainable mitigation of methane emission from livestock farming. *J. Clean. Prod.* 213, 915–925. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jclepro.2018.12.233>.
- Ulyatt, M.J., Thomson, D.J., Beever, D.E., Evans, R.T., Haines, M.J., 1988. The digestion of perennial ryegrass (*Lolium perenne* cv. Melle) and white clover (*Trifolium repens* cv. Blanca) by grazing cattle. *Br. J. Nutr.* 60 (1), 137–149. <https://doi.org/10.1079/bjn19880083>.
- Ulyatt, M.J., Lassey, K.R., Shelton, I.D., Walker, C.F., 2005. Methane emission from sheep grazing four pastures in late summer in New Zealand. *N. Z. J. Agric. Res.* 48 (4), 385–390. <https://doi.org/10.1080/00288233.2005.9513671>.
- van Dorland, H.A., Wettstein, H.R., Leuenberger, H., Kreuzer, M., 2007. Effect of supplementation of fresh and ensiled clovers to ryegrass on nitrogen loss and methane emission of dairy cows. *Livest. Sci.* 111 (1–2), 57–69. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.livsci.2006.11.015>.
- van Gastelen, S., Antunes-Fernandes, E.C., Hettinga, K.A., Klop, G., Alferink, S.J.J., Hendriks, W.H., Dijkstra, J., 2015. Enteric methane production, rumen volatile fatty acid concentrations, and milk fatty acid composition in lactating Holstein-Friesian cows fed grass silage- or corn silage-based diets. *J. Dairy Sci.* 98 (3), 1915–1927. <https://doi.org/10.3168/jds.2014-8552>.
- van Gastelen, S., Visker, M.H.P.W., Edwards, J.E., Antunes-Fernandes, E.C., Hettinga, K.A., Alferink, S.J.J., Hendriks, W.H., Bovenhuis, H., Smidt, H., Dijkstra, J., 2017. Linseed oil and DGAT1 K232A polymorphism: effects on methane emission, energy and nitrogen metabolism, lactation performance, ruminal fermentation, and rumen microbial composition of Holstein-Friesian cows. *J. Dairy Sci.* 100 (11), 8939–8957. <https://doi.org/10.3168/jds.2016-12367>.
- van Gastelen, S., Dijkstra, J., Bannink, A., 2019. Are dietary strategies to mitigate enteric methane emission equally effective across dairy cattle, beef cattle, and sheep? *J. Dairy Sci.* 102 (7), 6109–6130. <https://doi.org/10.3168/jds.2018-15785>.
- van Lingen, H.J., Niu, M., Kebreab, E., Valadares Filho, S.C., Rooke, J.A., Duthie, C.A., Schwarm, A., Kreuzer, M., Hynd, P.I., Caetano, M., Eugène, M., Martin, C., McGee, M., O'Kiely, P., Hünerberg, M., McAllister, T.A., Berchielli, T.T., Messana, J.D., Peiren, N., Hristov, A.N., 2019. Prediction of enteric methane production, yield and intensity of beef cattle using an intercontinental database. *Agric., Ecosyst. Environ.* 283 (December 2018), 106575 <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.agee.2019.106575>.
- van Wyngaard, J.D.V., Meeske, R., Erasmus, L.J., 2018. Effect of concentrate level on enteric methane emissions, production performance, and rumen fermentation of Jersey cows grazing kikuyu-dominant pasture during summer. *J. Dairy Sci.* 101 (11), 9954–9966. <https://doi.org/10.3168/jds.2017-14327>.
- van Zijderveld, S.M., Dijkstra, J., Perdok, H.B., Newbold, J.R., Gerrits, W.J.J., 2011. Dietary inclusion of diallyl disulfide, yucca powder, calcium fumarate, an extruded linseed product, or medium-chain fatty acids does not affect methane production in lactating dairy cows. *J. Dairy Sci.* 94 (6), 3094–3104. <https://doi.org/10.3168/jds.2010-4042>.
- Varga, K., Fehér, J., Trugly, B., Drexler, D., Leiber, F., Verrastro, V., Magid, J., Chylinski, C., Athanasiadou, S., Thuerig, B., László, A., Ladányi, M., Moeskops, B., Herforth-Rahmé, J., Tamm, L., 2022. The state of play of copper, mineral oil, external nutrient input, anthelmintics, antibiotics and vitamin usage and available reduction strategies in organic farming across Europe. *Sustain.* 14 (6). <https://doi.org/10.3390/su14063182>.
- Vargas, J., Ungerfeld, E., Muñoz, C., Dilorenzo, N., 2022. Feeding strategies to mitigate enteric methane emission from ruminants in grassland systems. *Animals* 12 (9), 1–13. <https://doi.org/10.3390/ani12091132>.
- Vasta, V., Daghigh, M., Cappucci, A., Buccioli, A., Serra, A., Viti, C., Mele, M., 2019. Invited review: Plant polyphenols and rumen microbiota responsible for fatty acid biohydrogenation, fiber digestion, and methane emission: experimental evidence and methodological approaches. *J. Dairy Sci.* 102 (5), 3781–3804. <https://doi.org/10.3168/jds.2018-14985>.
- Veneman, J.B., Muetzel, S., Hart, K.J., Faulkner, C.L., Moorby, J.M., Perdok, H.B., Newbold, C.J., 2015. Does dietary mitigation of enteric methane production affect rumen function and animal productivity in dairy cows? *PLoS One* 10 (10), 1–18. <https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pone.0140282>.
- Waghorn, G.C., Tavendale, M.H., Woodfield, D.R., 2002. Methanogenesis from forages fed to sheep. *Proc. N. Z. Grassl. Assoc.* 167–171. <https://doi.org/10.33584/jnzg.2002.64.2462>.
- Wang, C., Wang, S., Zhou, H., Glindemann, T., 2007. Effects of forage composition and growing season on methane emission from sheep in the Inner Mongolia steppe of China. *Ecol. Res.* 22 (1), 41–48. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11284-006-0191-9>.
- Wang, C.J., Wang, S.P., Zhou, H., 2009. Influences of flavomycin, ropadiar, and saponin on nutrient digestibility, rumen fermentation, and methane emission from sheep. *Anim. Feed Sci. Technol.* 148 (2–4), 157–166. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.anifeeds.2008.03.008>.
- Wang, S., Terranova, M., Kreuzer, M., Marquardt, S., Eggerschwiler, L., Schwarm, A., 2018. Supplementation of pelleted hazel (*Corylus avellana*) leaves decreases methane and urinary nitrogen emissions by sheep at unchanged forage intake. *Sci. Rep.* 8 (1), 1–10. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41598-018-23572-3>.
- Warner, D., Podesta, S.C., Hatew, B., Klop, G., van Laar, H., Bannink, A., Dijkstra, J., 2015. Effect of nitrogen fertilization rate and regrowth interval of grass herbage on methane emission of zero-grazing lactating dairy cows. *J. Dairy Sci.* 98 (5), 3383–3393. <https://doi.org/10.3168/jds.2014-9068>.
- Warner, D., Hatew, B., Podesta, S.C., Klop, G., Van Gastelen, S., Van Laar, H., Dijkstra, J., Bannink, A., 2016. Effects of nitrogen fertilization rate and maturity of grass silage on methane emission by lactating dairy cows. *Animal* 10 (1), 34–43. <https://doi.org/10.1017/S1751731115001640>.
- Warner, D., Bannink, A., Hatew, B., van Laar, H., Dijkstra, J., 2017. Effects of grass silage quality and level of feed intake on enteric methane production in lactating dairy cows. *J. Anim. Sci.* 95 (8), 3687. <https://doi.org/10.2527/jas2017.1459>.
- Wilkinson, J.M., 2011. Re-defining efficiency of feed use by livestock. *Animal* 5 (7), 1014–1022. <https://doi.org/10.1017/S175173111100005X>.
- Wilson, R.L., Bionaz, M., MacAdam, J.W., Beauchemin, K.A., Naumann, H.D., Ates, S., 2020. Milk production, nitrogen utilization, and methane emissions of dairy cows grazing grass, forb, and legume-based pastures. *J. Anim. Sci.* 98 (7). <https://doi.org/10.1093/jas/skaa220>.
- Wims, C.M., Deighton, M.H., Lewis, E., O'Loughlin, B., Delaby, L., Boland, T.M., O'Donovan, M., 2010. Effect of pregrazing herbage mass on methane production, dry matter intake, and milk production of grazing dairy cows during the mid-season period. *J. Dairy Sci.* 93 (10), 4976–4985. <https://doi.org/10.3168/jds.2010-3245>.
- Winders, T.M., Jolly-Breithaupt, M.L., Wilson, H.C., MacDonald, J.C., Erickson, G.E., Watson, A.K., 2019. Evaluation of the effects of biochar on diet digestibility and methane production from growing and finishing steers. *Transl. Anim. Sci.* 3 (2), 775–783. <https://doi.org/10.1093/tas/txz027>.
- Woodward, S.L., Waghorn, G.C., Ulyatt, M.J., Lassey, K.R., 2001. Early indications that feeding *Lotus* will reduce methane emissions from ruminants. *Proc. N. Z. Soc. Anim. Prod.* 61, 23–26.
- Woodward, S.L., Waghorn, G.C., Lassey, K.R., Laboyrie, P.G., 2002. Does feeding *sulla* (*Hedysarum coronarium*) reduce methane emissions from dairy cows? *Proc. N. Z. Soc. Anim. Prod.* 62, 227–230.
- Woodward, S.L., Waghorn, G.C., Laboyrie, P., 2004. Condensed tannins in birdsfoot trefoil (*Lotus corniculatus*) reduce methane emissions from dairy cows. *Proc. N. Z. Soc. Anim. Prod.* 64, 160–164.
- Woodward, S.L., Waghorn, G.C., Thomson, N.A., 2006. Supplementing dairy cows with oils to improve performance and reduce methane – does it work? *Proc. N. Z. Soc. Anim. Prod.* 66, 176–181.

- Yang, C.T., Wang, C.M., Zhao, Y.G., Chen, T.B., Aubry, A., Gordon, A.W., Yan, T., 2021. Effects of feeding level on enteric methane emissions and utilisation of energy and nitrogen in dry ewes of two genotypes offered fresh ryegrass. *Small Rumin. Res.* 199, 106381 <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.smallrumres.2021.106381>.
- Yumashev, D., Janes-Bassett, V., Redhead, J.W., Rowe, E.C., Davies, J., 2022. Terrestrial carbon sequestration under future climate, nutrient and land use change and management scenarios: a national-scale UK case study. *Environ. Res. Lett.* 17 (11) <https://doi.org/10.1088/1748-9326/aca037>.
- Zeitz, J.O., Soliva, C.R., Kreuzer, M., 2012. Swiss diet types for cattle: how accurately are they reflected by the Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change default values? *J. Integr. Environ. Sci.* 9 (SUPPL. 1), 199–216. <https://doi.org/10.1080/1943815X.2012.709253>.
- Zhang, F., Li, B., Ban, Z., Liang, H., Li, L., Zhao, W., Yan, X., 2021. Evaluation of origanum oil, hydrolysable tannins and tea saponin in mitigating ruminant methane: In vitro and in vivo methods. *J. Anim. Physiol. Anim. Nutr.* 105 (4), 630–638. <https://doi.org/10.1111/jpn.13501>.
- Zhao, Y.G., Aubry, A., Annett, R., O'Connell, N.E., Yan, T., 2016. Enteric methane emissions and nitrogen utilisation efficiency for two genotype of hill hoggets offered fresh, ensiled and pelleted ryegrass. *Livest. Sci.* 188, 1–8. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.livsci.2016.03.016>.
- Zhao, Y.G., Annett, R., Yan, T., 2017. Effects of forage types on digestibility, methane emissions, and nitrogen utilization efficiency in two genotypes of hill ewes. *J. Anim. Sci.* 95 (8), 3762. <https://doi.org/10.2527/jas2017.1598>.